

An interpretative explanatory study of the arrest warrants wording against High State Public Elected Official of the Russian Federation (Part II)

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Abstract

The major topic of the current study attempts to provide an interpretative explanatory point of view of the logic of “*doing Justice*” by the *Rome Statute* (RS)^[1]. There are tackled concepts of category crimes called *Crimes against humanity* and *War Crimes*, however, concentrating on Ukraine-Russia bilateral relations over recent decades. The major focus is on text of arrest warrants (AWTs) against a High State Public Elected Official, *i.e.*, the President of the Russian Federation (hereafter **Subject 1**)^[2]. As Part I^[3] of the relevant study, the current one aims at seeking meaning and understanding of documents, facts, evidences, and arguments; if any, based on developed and applied tools, concepts, theories, and laws used to *do Justice*, internationally within the International Criminal Tribunals (ICTs). However, Part II details on what Judicial Authorities, globally mean by terms *War Crimes* and *Crimes against humanity*; thus, attempting to fill gap of knowledge of whether they are explicit theorizing about *non-State* and *State actors* as well as the so-called “*Organizational Policy*”. Because, due to already adopted so diverse contexts of the terms, there could not be operated with only one common understanding of them regarding requirements satisfying Article 7^[1] dealing with *Crimes against humanity*. The reader’s attention is particularly focusing on term *Organization*. It could be treated as having a “*state-like*” nature; thus, satisfying Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. In the latter context, this study seeks to establish mutual connections among understandings of standards satisfying Article 25(1), Article 25(3)(a), Article 25(3)(c), Article 25(3)(d), and Article 7(2)(a) and Article 7(1)(d) in addition to Article 28(b) of the RS^[1]. There is also detailed on Article 7(1) and Article 7(3) of the *Statute of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia* (ICTY)^[4] tackling the issue of the *Individual Criminal Responsibility*; thus, differentiating and varying understanding of terms *State* or *Organizational policy* within ICTs. The common notion of *Organization* refers to any organized group of people, including non-State armed group (NSAG). The Article 7^[1] has a broad scope of prosecutions for *Crimes against humanity* allowing not only to implement a State support to such crimes, but also to include any type of aforementioned organizations even a highly theoretical “*organization*” of only two people. Comprehensive knowledge of aforementioned connections is crucial not only for adequate understanding of AWTs^[2] and the logic of “*doing Justice*”, but also for reliably assessing effectiveness of *Rome Statute*^[1]. Frequently, ICTs tended to use both *War crimes* and *Crimes against humanity* charges to penalize same crime conduct; if any. Thus, whether or not an AWT could be extended to cover charge of various crimes is of significant concern. However, events of political violence in many countries globally; for instance, Côte d'Ivoire, Syria, Egypt, Libya, Kenya, Nigeria, or Ukraine (2014) ones cause for doubts about the effectiveness the *Rome Statute*^[1] due to expanding the concept of the *Crimes against humanity*. It at least theoretically might extend broadly the range of so-called crime actors. In other words, the “*doing Justice*” under the *Rome Statute*^[1] might face problems due to the fact that the discussed crimes could be understood in more liberal terms; thus, involving innocent individual as hypothetical accused. Despite, that the views, herein, are the author’s alone ones, they are argued by relevantly cited expert opinions; thus, allowing to incentivize to claim that the aforementioned terms could mean something different beyond straightforward “*State*”, “*Organization*”, and “*Policy*” requirements. One of the five key elements inherent in *Crimes against humanity* is “*a State or organizational policy*”. This text is associated and agreed with, as well as does not contradict the Article 70 of the *Rome Statute*^[1].

Introduction

Briefly, Part I^[3] of an interpretative explanatory study of AWTs^[2] has attempted to explain and to discuss meaning and interpretation of words and various groups of words within the framework of certain context of definitions of *War Crimes* under Article 8(2)(a)(vii)^[1] and Article 8(2)(b)(viii)^[1], as far as AWTs^[2] hypothesize committed such category crimes; thus, stating:

“Situation in Ukraine: [...] arrest warrants against **Subject 1** and **Subject 2** (Press Release: 17 March 2023)
Today, 17 March 2023, [...] issued warrants of arrest for two individuals in the context of the situation in Ukraine: Mr **Subject 1** and Ms **Subject 2**.
Mr **Subject 1**, born on XXX, President of the Russian Federation, is allegedly responsible for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population (**children**) and that of unlawful transfer of population (children) from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation (under **articles 8(2)(a)(vii) and 8(2)(b)(viii) of the Rome Statute**). The crimes were allegedly committed **in Ukrainian occupied territory at least from 24 February 2022**. There are reasonable grounds to believe that Mr **Subject 1** bears individual criminal responsibility for the aforementioned crimes, (i) for having committed the acts directly, jointly with others and/or through others (**article 25(3)(a) of the Rome Statute**), and (ii) for his failure to exercise control properly over civilian and military subordinates who committed the acts, or allowed for their commission, and who were under his effective authority and control, pursuant to superior responsibility (**article 28(b) of the Rome Statute**).
Ms **Subject 2**, born on XXX, Commissioner for Children’s Rights in the Office of the President of the Russian Federation, is allegedly responsible for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population (children) and that of unlawful transfer of population (children) from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation (under **articles 8(2)(a)(vii) and 8(2)(b)(viii) of the Rome Statute**). The crimes were allegedly committed **in Ukrainian occupied territory at least from 24 February 2022**. There are reasonable grounds to believe that Ms **Subject 2** bears individual criminal responsibility for the aforementioned crimes, for having committed the acts directly, jointly with others and/or through others (**article 25(3)(a) of the Rome Statute**).
[...] based on the Prosecution’s applications of 22 February 2023, that there are reasonable grounds to believe that each suspect bears responsibility for the war crime of unlawful deportation of population and that of unlawful transfer of population from occupied areas of Ukraine to the Russian Federation, in prejudice of Ukrainian children.
The [...] considered that the warrants are secret in order to protect victims and witnesses and also to safeguard the investigation. Nevertheless, mindful that the conduct addressed in the present situation is allegedly ongoing, and that the public awareness of the warrants may contribute to the prevention of the further commission of crimes, the [...] considered that it is in the interests of justice to authorise the Registry to publicly disclose the existence of the warrants, the name of the suspects, the crimes for which the warrants are issued, and the modes of liability as established by the Chamber.
The above-mentioned warrants of arrests were issued pursuant to the applications submitted by the Prosecution on 22 February 2023”^[2(a)]. There is also a text of arrest warrant addressing the same issue (please, consider^[2(b)]).

Both the Part I^[3] and Part II of the study primarily aim at winning some form of argument about how practically AWTs^[2] wording is applied to ICTs, including to RS^[1]. Due to direct connection with legal definitions and punishment for committed crimes, Part I^[3] also has attempted to shed more light on mechanisms of *doing Justice via* interpreting the term ‘*Individual Criminal Responsibility*’ (ICR) under Article 25^[1], Article 28^[1], and Article 30^[1].

The complexity of the matter involves linguistics, cognitive science, logic, philosophy of Justice, and, more. To a certain extent it could cause for ambiguity by applying specific terms. Thus, Part II attempts to bridge gap between application of common words and groups of words to define *War Crimes* and *Crimes against humanity* again in the context of AWTs^[2].

Why, there is attempted to do so?

The logic of “*doing Justice*” by the RS^[1] is based on deterrence and retributive foundations^[5]. The retribution refers to punish every single offender^[6]. The deterrence is significantly complicated, due to argue about a broad spectrum of conceptions of crimes under the RS^[1] allowing for prosecuting a broader range of offenders, including political leaders and High State Public Elected Officials.

Looking at definitions of *War Crimes* under the RS^[1] as Part I^[3] has attempted to do, and those of *Crimes against humanity* which are tackled, herein, there has been stressed on a problem that the crime categories could be understood in a significantly more liberal terms; thus, expanding understanding of them and negatively affecting on effectiveness of “*doing Justice*” practically.

Remarks on, have been made tackling political violence in; for instance, looking at events in Egypt^[7], Côte d'Ivoire^[8], Kenya [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010] (below), Libya^[9], Ukraine (2014)^[10], and more. There is raised doubt with respect to the effectiveness of the process, due to expanding understanding of terms constituting *Crimes against humanity*. As aforementioned, there are a set of words and group-words common to both the *War Crimes* and *Crimes against humanity* looking at the AWTs^[2].

Theoretically, the *Crimes against humanity* might involve a large number of perpetrators. It is rather an obstacle to deterrence; thus, contradicting to foundations of *doing Justice* and *International Criminal Code*. This fact is regarded as a serious concern, amongst others, because "*Demarcation line between crimes against humanity" and other crimes might eventually blur"*.

In addition to the latter problem, there is also a problem with selective prosecutions^[11] as preconditions for a politicizing of "*doing Justice*" practically instead of seeking of *Individual Criminal Responsibility* and punishing of perpetrators of crimes.

Therefore, Part II attempts to further provide pro-arguments about a view that the AWTs^[2] provide a broader interpretation of words and group of terms, thus, allowing for not only expanding Article 25(3)(a)^[1] to inconsistency with Article 22(2)^[1], but also for re-categorizing crimes and for adding of crimes — a fact, which have been broadly criticised, as well.

Article 22^[1] (Nullum crimen sine lege)

2. *The definition of a crime shall be strictly construed and shall not be extended by analogy.*

In case of ambiguity, the definition shall be interpreted in favour of the person being investigated, prosecuted or convicted.

Owing to a lack of hierarchy among category crimes under Articles 6^[1], Article 7^[1], and Article 8^[1], I would like to focus the reader's attention on a parallel considering of Article 25(3)(a)^[1] with Article 25(1)^[1], Article 25(3)(c)^[1], Article 25(3)(d)^[1], as well as Article 7(2)(a)^[1] and Article 7(1)(d)^[1] in addition to Article 28(b)^[1] looking mostly at cases of the ICTs practice, including those ones involving political leaders. However, there is chiefly concentrated on the definitions, notions, and applications of the terms "Policy", "Plane", "State", "Attack", and "Organization", respectively. IN opposite to Part I^[1] content, this study attempts to shape the demarcation line between the two 'Policy' and "Plane" used to various ICTs Statutes.

As Part I^[3] has already shown, I hope enough illustratively, there is made parallel considering with actual executive power authority of the Presidential Institution of the Russian Federation, Federal Laws and their inter-Institutional Codes; thus, attempting to further argue for adequacy of the author's statement.

1. The wording of the arrest warrants – a legal meaning from perspective of *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute

As the introductory section has shown, AWTs^[2] refer for *War crime* of “unlawful” “deportation” of population; furthermore, children and that of “unlawful transfer” of population (children) from areas of Ukraine(?!)^[3] to the Russian Federation; thus, highlighting on AWTs^[2] hypotheses that **Subject 1** bears ICR under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] and Article 28(b)^[1].

First, and foremost there lies a logic question: Could an innocent individual as **Subject 1** be involved into *Crimes against humanity*, despite the AWTs^[2] hypotheses for *War crime*, explicitly highlighting the fact that he has been and currently occupies High State Public Elected Official Administrative position?

The AWTs^[2] have been written, in fact, against Article 22^[1]. They illustrate a lack of strict definition of a crime (Part I^[3]), which, further must be strictly construed and must not be extended by analogy. In addition, terms as “State”, “Policy”, and “Organization” under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] allow for interpretation variation within a set of concepts dealing with violence committed by both the State and non-State perpetrators, who presumably should operate in an organized manner. Preliminary, I would like to stress that the answer to the latter question is: Yes, he as innocent individual could be involved into.

The latter assumption raises the next logic question: How there could be linked **Article 8(2)(a)(vii)** and **Article 8(2)(b)(viii)** of AWTs^[2] with *Crimes against humanity* under Article 7^[1]?

To address this question let us, first, concentrate on texts of Elements of the Crimes^[12]:

8(2)(a)(vii)-1 War crime of unlawful deportation and transfer.

8(2)(a)(vii)-2 War crime of unlawful confinement.

8(2)(b)(viii) The transfer, directly or indirectly, by the Occupying Power of parts of its own civilian population into the territory it occupies, or the deportation or transfer of all or parts of the population of the occupied territory within or outside this territory.

Article 7^[1] Crimes against humanity

1. For the purpose of this Statute, “crime against humanity” means any of the following acts when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack:

(c) Enslavement;

(d) Deportation or forcible transfer of population

(i) Enforced disappearance of persons;

(i) “Enforced disappearance of persons” means the arrest, detention or abduction of persons by, or with the authorization, support or acquiescence of, a State or a political organization, followed by a refusal to acknowledge that deprivation of freedom or to give information on the fate or whereabouts of those persons, with the intention of removing them from the protection of the law for a prolonged period of time.

Article 7(2)(a)

2. For the purpose of paragraph 1:

(a) “Attack directed against any civilian population” means a course of conduct involving the multiple commission of acts referred to in paragraph 1 against any civilian population, pursuant to or in furtherance of a State or organizational policy to commit such attack.

As could be seen words ‘*deportation*’ and ‘*transfer*’ occur in Article 7^[1], Article 8(2)(a)(vii)^[1] and Article 8(2)(b)(viii)^[1]. So, how one should distinguish among them and texts of Article 7^[1], Article 8(2)(a)(vii)^[1] and Article 8(2)(b)(viii)^[1]?

The Article 7(2)(a)^[1] details on a complex term “*Attack directed against a civilian population*”. It is understood as crime involving a set of acts shown in Article 7^[1], Paragraph 1 against any civilian population. The notion of “Attack” for purposes of *Crimes against humanity* is different from meaning of “Attack” in a context of combat, involving armed forces and seizing or defending a position^[13].

Particularly, Article 7(1)(d)^[1] treats crimes of “deportation” or “transfer” of population. They should be carried out in furtherance of, or agreed with a “State” or corresponding “Organizational policy”. A particular remark on: The conducts do not need to constitute a military attack. Rather, there is reflected in mind “Policy to carry out such attack” and “State” or “Organization” which encourage and promote such attack [ICC-01/04-01/07/30.09.2008, §393][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2008_05172.PDF]; [ICC-01/05-01/08/15.06.2009, §79][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2009_04528.PDF]).

Obviously, Article 7(2)(a)^[1] links with Article 25(3)(a)^[1] (Figures 1 and 2) in the context of the interpretative explanatory study of AWTs^[2]. Article 7(2)(a)^[1] contains a precondition on existing of an “Attack” which could involve “State” or “Organizational policy” to carry out it^[14].

Figure 1. A parallel considering of Article 25(3)(a)^[1] with Article 25(1)^[1], Article 25(3)(c)^[1], Article 25(3)(d)^[1], as well as Article 7(2)(a)^[1] and Article 7(1)(d)^[1] in addition to Article 28(b)^[1] within ICTs cases; (continued as Figure 2) (see high resolution figure as supporting information).

[1] A. Cassese, *J. Gen. Int. Crim. L.*, 3rd ed. Oxford, Oxford University Press (2013) p. 175.
 [2] R. Dworkin, *Just Cases, Exceptional and the Search for, Crim. L. Forum* 20 (2009) 263-287 (DOI 10.1007/s10992-009-9066-8).
 [3] J. Olin, *Joint Intention in Criminal Law*, *Chicago Journal of International Law*, 11 (2011) Article 26 (https://www.jstor.org/stable/41396049/41396049.pdf?pdfcrisis=1).

Figure 2. A parallel considering of Article 25(3)(a)^[1] with Article 25(3)(d)^[1], Article 7(2)(a)^[1] and Article 7(1)(d)^[1] (see high resolution figure as supporting information).

1.1. What there should be understood by "Policy", "State or organizational", "Widespread", "Systematic", and "Attack directed against a civilian population"?

There are established three components require to Article 7(2)(a)^[1]:

- (i) The existence of a State or an 'organization';
- (ii) a policy to commit such attack; and
- (iii) a link between the multiple commission of acts referred to in Article 7(1) of the Statute and the policy of such State or 'organization' [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §§ 84–93][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

The "Policy" and "State or organizational" requirements must be analyzed separately. For purposes of Article 7(2)(a)^[1], however, they are linked. When, multiply committed crimes occur, then Article 7(2)(a)^[1] links to Article 7(1)^[1]. There should be a conduct involving a set of crime acts. They are enumerated in Article 7(1)^[1] against any civilians, who according to AWTs^[2] are children.

Moreover, such a policy; if any, might be further implemented into deliberate failure to act; thus, attempting to encourage an attack. A common understanding is that such a policy could not be inferred solely lacking of corresponding governmental or other organizational activity. Thus, the role of the Government or corresponding State Authorities is implemented.

Therefore, an "attack directed against any civilian population" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] refers to a conduct consisting of multiple commissions of crimes against any civilian population, pursuant to or in furtherance of a State or organizational policy to commit such attack.

Connecting Article 7(2)(a)^[1] with Article 7(1)^[1], one could expect to understand how he, respectively, she could distinguish among same type crime. An answer is provided:

"[T]he expression "widespread or systematic" in article 7(1) of the Statute excludes random or isolated acts of violence. Furthermore, the adjective "widespread" connotes the large scale nature of the attack and the number of targeted persons, whereas the adjective "systematic" refers to the organised nature of the acts of violence and the improbability of their random occurrence".

There is added to term 'Attack' corresponding terms "widespread" or "systematic", which are not specifically defined in the RS^[1], however [ICC-01/04-01/07/30.09.2008, §393][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2008_05172.PDF].

Looking at the statement above, a distinguishing criterion on Article 7(2)(a)^[1] and Article 7(1)^[1] refers mostly to scale of committed crimes within the framework of same type of crimes.

Accounting for the fact, that there is excluded from isolated or random crimes from the notion of *Crimes against humanity* there is added requirement that the conducts must be directed against a civilian "population". The 'Attack' should be either "*widespread*" which refers to number of victims, or it should be "*Systematic*"; thus, indicating methodical plan or a pattern [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 648][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/tjug/en/tad-ts70507JT2-e.pdf>].

In addition to the fact that the Rome Statute does not explicitly clarify the terms "widespread" or "systematic", there is further a rather lack of clear demarcation line between 'Plan' and 'Policy', but the term "*Systematic*" involves 'Plan'.

On the other hand, there is definition of 'Policy'; for instance, the following one:

"[I]n the context of a widespread attack, the requirement of an organisational policy pursuant to article 7(2) (a) of the Statute ensures that the attack, even if carried out over a large geographical area or directed against a large number of victims, must still be thoroughly organised and follow a regular pattern. It must also be conducted in furtherance of a common policy involving public or private resources...The policy need not be explicitly defined by the organisational group. Indeed, an attack which is planned, directed or organised - as opposed to spontaneous or isolated acts of violence - will satisfy this criterion" [ICC-01/04-01/07/30.09.2008,§396][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2008_05172.PDF].

It could be also said that despite that a "scale" of committed crimes could be used as distinguishing criterion between crimes Article 7(2)(a)^[1] and Article 7(1)^[1] based on expression "widespread" in Article 7(1)^[1], referring as aforementioned to "*number of victims*" the word '*widespread*' in context "Attack" is involved in defining requirements of organisational policy within the Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. Therefore, the requirements for "Organizational policy", herein, rather refer to "number of victims", instead of to "a methodical plan or a pattern".

Perhaps, the current study should meet additional criticism if there is written that connotation of word '*widespread*' itself involves both temporal and spatial dimensions. How '*widespread*' should be an attack in order to distinguish precisely between requirements for "Organisational policy" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1], i.e., how '*widespread*' is inked with "*systematic*" within the case of multiply committed crimes over a large territory and extended temporal dimension of the crime? Moreover, a common view states that the 'attack' must be beyond spontaneous or isolated acts of violence. Thus, the wording "*widespread attack*" excludes from isolated acts of violence. How one should distinguish among mass crimes and conducts due to '*widespread* and *systematic* attack' or 'Policy' within the numerous crimes and a large spatial and temporal distribution of them? (below)

As an attempt to shed more light on the issue, there could be cited [ICC-01/05-01/08/15.06.2009, §81][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2009_04528.PDF] statement, that "*multiple commission of acts*" means more than a few isolated incidents according to Article 7(1)^[1]. The connotation of word 'few' involves more than two (2) and less than five (5) acts. If there is connected the latter statement with the understanding of "widespread" under Article 7(1)^[1], then, for instance, six (6) mutually connected acts should be regarded as exhibiting a large scale nature.

Further: When an "Attack" is classified as '*widespread*'; there is not needed to consider whether it is also a '*systematic*' one. When, it is not needed to do so, then it is not needed to detail on its "methodical plan" or "a pattern"; if any [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 648].

In other words, on the one hand, the Rome Statute does not define the terms "widespread" or "systematic" examining the nature of an "Attack"; if any. On the other hand, even if it is examined, there is not needed to account for the 'systematic' nature of the 'Attack' or for its hypothetical "methodical plan" or "a pattern". Then, why AWTs^[2] are issued against High State Public Elected Official individual involved into hypothetical War Crimes, which are conduct type crimes; furthermore, under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] and Article 28(b)^[1] which assume an indirect perpetration of crime? For the author the answer to the latter question is obvious. I strongly hope that the various parts of my study devoted to the issue should convince also the reader for the reliability and the adequacy of my statements about this case and the AWTs^[2].

Thus, it should be further emphasised on requirements for Article 7^[1] which should be strictly considered word-by-word, as preceding paragraphs have attempted to illustrate, looking at terms 'widespread', 'systematic', "policy", "plan" and "state or organizational". It seems to me that the issue is one of the most difficult, because of it assumes, as shown above, unambiguous definitions of terms, however, frequently, there is a lack of such definitions.

Since, this study cannot attempt exhaust the connotation and notion of the discussed terms, but of a particular importance would be a clear demarcation line among commonly recognized and adopted views restricting their applications to various category crimes within ICTs, it should be noted that neither 'plan' nor 'policy' or 'scale' as terms are elements of *War crimes* under *Customary law*.

However, they determine whether or not to carry out investigations against a hypothesized accused. Particularly, challenging are cases involving hypothesized accused occupying High State Public Elected Official positions due to request for strict structural framework accommodating all these terms. Because, within the framework of, for instance the Joint Criminal Enterprise (JCE) doctrine there are involved two individuals; thus, tackling superior-subordinate relations. It is a tool for establishing various degree of ICR and the JCE liability is implicitly allowed for Article 25(3)(a)^[1], due to reference to '*committing a crime jointly with another*'^[15]. The latter assumes a plan or common pattern of activities not only causing for, but also ensuring the committed crimes. The JEC doctrine includes indirect co-perpetration of a conduct *via* "planning" and "coordinating".

Therefore, the concept of "a plan" or "a policy" is, in fact, involved into requirements for Article 25(3)(a)^[1]. Apart, from a dismissal of defence claim that concept of co-perpetration under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] is based on JCE notion, as opposed to notion of CC^[16] (**Figure 1**); thus, further stressing on variation of doctrines applied to crimes detailed on AWTs^[2]:

(i)...jointly with others and/or through others (Article 25(3)(a)^[1]).

Looking at definitions of *War crimes* under the RS^[1] there is also highlighted unnecessarily narrow fashion of shaping them.

The "unlawful" attack provisions, for instance, connect to "intentionally" launching or to directing attacks. Conversely, ICTY^[4] Statute applies the term "wilful" both incorporating "intention" in addition to 'a high degree of "recklessness".

"...wilfully: the accused must have acted consciously and with intent, i.e., with his mind on the act and its consequences, and willing them ('criminal intent' or 'malice aforethought'); this encompasses the concepts of 'wrongful intent' or 'recklessness', viz., the attitude of an agent who, without being certain of a particular result, accepts the possibility of it happening; on the other hand, ordinary negligence or lack of foresight is not covered, i.e., when a man acts without having his mind on the act or its consequences" [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, § 54][<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/40194>]. The notion of "wilfully" incorporates recklessness. It excludes from mere negligence. The actor who recklessly attacks civilians acts "wilfully". Despite, the fact that the discussed elements are common to crimes under Article 3^[4] (Violations of the laws or customs of war) of the ICTY^[4] Statute; thus, highlighting specific elements — consider, for instance [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, § 56] — the word 'wilful' is common to most type crimes under Article 2^[4] (Grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions of 1949) of ICTY Statute involving: (a) wilful killing; (c) wilfully causing great suffering or serious injury to body or health; (f) wilfully depriving a prisoner..., in addition to (g) unlawful deportation or transfer or unlawful confinement of a civilian; among other crimes. Owing to a lack of hierarchy among the various category crimes, there could be assumed that

the term "wilful" incorporating both the "intention" and 'a high degree of "recklessness" should be equally applicable to crimes under Article 2^[4] and Article 3^[4] of ICTY Statute.

Disputable is the issue how one might respond to an argument that a hypothesized accused might have attacked civilian population, but he, respectively, she didn't intend to do so^[13].

At this point, I would like to discuss a term "indiscriminate attacks", as well. Because, looking at the major purpose of this study the **sub-section 1.3** focuses the reader attention on a case involving "three groups of 85 children and accompanying adults who concerned crossed the border and entered the Russian Federation" (below).

What there should be understood under "indiscriminate attacks"?

"As regards the first element, the Trial Chamber agrees with previous Trial Chambers that indiscriminate attacks, that is to say, attacks which strike civilians or civilian objects and military objectives without distinction, may qualify as direct attacks against civilians" [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, § 57] and

"One type of indiscriminate attack violates the principle of proportionality. The practical application of the principle of distinction requires that those who plan or launch an attack take all feasible precautions to verify that the objectives attacked are neither civilians nor civilian objects, so as to spare civilians as much as possible" [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, § 58].

(The term "civilians" excludes from combatants. It refers to "all non-combatants within the meaning of common Article 3 to the [Geneva] Conventions". The concept of "non-combatants" is not always clear in application [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 637]. It is relatively broadly defined and includes resistance fighters or hospital patients, as well.)

Looking at the latter statements, I would like to stress on the wording "those who plan or launch an attack take all feasible precautions to verify that the objectives attacked are neither civilians nor civilian objects", which returns us to my starting point asking "How **Subject 1** as hypothesized accused within the AWTs^[2] is involved into crimes (i)...jointly with others and/or through others (Article 25(3)(a)^[1]) and (ii) for his failure to exercise control properly over civilian and military subordinates who committed the acts, or allowed for their commission, and who were under his effective authority and control, pursuant to superior responsibility (Article 28(b)^[2]) of deportation or transfer of children, when the doctrines tackling superior-subordinate relations even applied to civilians request plane or pattern. However, those who plan or launch an attack are the same individuals who should verify that objectives attacked are neither civilians nor civilian subjects.

Although, as aforementioned, case [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003] refers to crimes under Article 3^[4] of ICTY Statute it is unquestionably an extremely important for shaping application of common terms and doctrines within the ICTs Statutes. The latter case-example, together with those ones discussed in the following sub-sections unambiguously highlight on the fact that the doctrines tackling superior-subordinate relations are developed and mostly applied to mid-low (military) group individuals or, perhaps, troops within the framework of a direct and effective command, control and authority, Thus, they are inapplicable to the hypothesised crimes within the AWTs^[2], thus, involving innocent individual **Subject 1** into category crimes under the RS^[1]. A particular remark on the latter context is that the "indirect superior responsibility" cannot be regarded as part of the ICTY^[4] legal framework. An attempt to insert it into ICTY^[4] Statute should be faulted.

Further: Under ICTY^[4] Statute, crimes involving "unlawful attacks against civilian population" have been prosecuted, so far, in five cases. These are [IT-95-14], [IT-95-14/2], [IT-98-29], [IT-01-42]and [IT-02-54], respectively. The cases [IT-95-14] and [IT-95-14/2] involve Bosnian-Croat accused in massacre by Bosnian-Croat forces. In case [IT-98-29], the accused was commander of Bosnian-Serb forces involved into shelling and sniping crimes against Sarajevo inhabitants. In case [IT-01-42], accused was commander of Yugoslav

National Army Forces involved into prosecution and unlawful shelling of Dubrovnik on 06.12.1991. In case [IT-02-54] in 2002, the accused as individual who has occupied High State Public Elected Official position is wrongly charged with ICR as indirect perpetrator of a large scale of crimes encompassing the whole spectrum of categories, including crimes in Sarajevo and Dubrovnik. In 2016 *post mortem* there has been drawn concluding statement about a lack of sufficient evidence. The latter charge is related with a very disputable term 'knowledge'. It is applied to various doctrines tackling crimes within superior-subordinate relations (Figures 1 and 2).

Moreover, the standards of "knowledge" vary, in both domestic Criminal Law and ICTs Statutes. There is a so-called "actual knowledge," corresponding to "intention". The term "intention" is linked to "should have known." It constitutes the so-called "negligence" and is directly linked with AWTs^[2] wording, showing: "(ii) for his failure to exercise control properly over civilian and military subordinates who committed the acts, or allowed for their commission, and who were under his effective authority and control, pursuant to superior responsibility (Article 28(b)^[1])". In the latter context, there should be added that term "general duty to know," does not reflect Customary International Law at the time of offences. As such it is not part of the ICTY^[4] legal framework. The term "had reason to know" requires proof that there was "information...available to him [superior] which would provide notice of crimes committed by his subordinates" [IT-96-21-T/16.11.1998, §346, §393; §§226–227][<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/1998/91857>].

The fact that the cognitive standard for superior responsibility is an extensively debatable legal issue at ICTs, thus, confusing accepted "actual knowledge" as the only appropriate standard for superior responsibility with "should have known" standard showing a much lower thresholds needs particular attention. Moreover, the terms 'intent' and 'plan' are mutually connected with the issue of how the individual intent should be involved into crimes that are mostly *collective ones* as *Crimes against humanity* or *Genocide*^[17]. The issue is very complex and difficult, because of the *Criminal law* is intended to treat *Individual criminal responsibility*, which appears not problematic when a hypothesized accused is charged with a crime that he, respectively, she has fully committed; or, the crime is on his or her own. Due to these reasons issue of so-called "knowledge" of a collective crimes linked with AWTs^[2], should be object of further my contribution.

However, among most disputable cases connected with "unlawful attacks" against civilian population is [IT-98-29] one. It treats crimes during armed conflicts, where military forces should distinguish among military subjects and objectives as well as civilians one. The term 'civilians,' also encompass individuals who are involved into hostilities. It is also narrowly defined; thus, difficult protection of civilians from attack when they are part of hostilities. The issue is relevant with cases of killed or injured civilians due to excessive application of principle of proportionality or in cases when military objectives are not separated from urban areas or civilians. Due to this reason in examining *actus reus* requirements for crimes there is assessed complex circumstances and surrounding facts which, frequently, are essential to distinguish among various acts of a collective crime.

The case [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003] also details on a shelling crime incident of Dobrinje football tournament on 01.06.1993. It involves at about 200 spectators, men, women, and children, who were watching a football game. Two shells exploded in a parking; thus, killing 12–16 persons and wounding within the 80–140 individuals. A large number of spectators and players were military staff or "military subjects". The Commander of ABiH 5th Motorized Dobrinja Brigade, to which belong the military staff was filed a report indicating 6 soldiers killed and 55 wounded as well as 5 civilians killed and 32 wounded [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, §377]. In this "unlawful attack", there were involves multiple crimes of shelling or sniping. As aforementioned the word 'unlawful' is involved into to (g) *unlawful deportation* or transfer or *unlawful confinement* of a civilian under Article 2^[4] of ICTY Statute. The case [IT-98-29] commonly treats also hundreds of killed civilians or wounded in Sarajevo by shelling or sniping during 1992-94. For the purpose of this study it is portent to note that it links from *micro-* to *macro-level* of collective crime events. It is essential and require a significant degree of precision in tackling these cases; furthermore, over a two year period. Furthermore, in this case, the accused is responsible for 15000 soldiers in the front lines. When there is a lack of direct evidence of orders, it appears a lack of reason to conclude that the accused as

commander bears command responsibility for discussed sniping. In such cases there would be reliable scientifically valid evidence linking cases of civilians who have been killed due to sniper fire from forces under direct command of the accused; if any. It allows for distinguishing from parallel cases which occur, but do not indicate unlawful attack. Owing to the fact that “*indirect superior responsibility*” cannot be regarded as part of ICTY^[4] Statute, it further assumes a seeking of additional scientific evidences within a case-by-case investigation; thus, excluding from pursuing an “indirect superior responsibility” for civilian authority or military commanders for committed crimes within a large and broad temporal and spatial framework.

Despite, there is agreement that Article 7^[1] defines relatively comprehensively the implemented category crimes; thus, including various modalities by committed crimes^[13].

However, then a hypothesised accused is charged with a crime having *collective character* and he, respectively, she is only indirectly involved into, there is a rather lack of ICR. Due to these reasons in cases of collective crimes a hypothesised accused, who is convicted and punished should be planned crime, in addition to individuals who merely participated in the crime^[17] as sketched above.

Despite, terms ‘*plan*’, ‘*intent*’, and ‘*knowledge*’ are implemented into requirements, establishing ICR for committing collective crimes. Looking at standards for *Genocide*^[17], there are further distinguished between “*individual intent*” and “*collective intent*” as crime elements. The latter one should be directed into destroying a strictly defined group people^[17]. In satisfying the *mens rea* standard of Genocide. There are particularly established individuals who lead or who plan the Crime as well as those who participate into it. Despite, that ATWs^[2] deals with *War crimes*, the presence of Article 25(3)(a)^[1] and Article 28(b)^[1] links the hypothesised accused with seeking ICR within a hypothesised committed *collective crime*; thus, causing for in-dept tackling of terms ‘*plan*’ and ‘*policy*’, and ‘*scale*’, among others. Nevertheless, that these terms are not elements of *War crimes*.

However, as sketched above, the so-called “*intention*” is directly connected with “*knowledge*”; thus, highlighting on subordinate crimes and is also very important ingredient — even, it is crucial element — of the superior responsibility doctrine.

In tackling *Crimes against humanity* there is stated that the “*accused acted with the element of intent necessary for the commission of crimes against humanity*” [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 641][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/tjug/en/tad-ts70507JT2-e.pdf>]. My highlights at this point are at the words ‘*intent*’ and ‘*act*’, because as Part I^[3] already has attempted to show that the *War crimes* are conduct type crimes; thus, applying standards for *actus reus* of hypothetical accrued as committing crime individually in the crime scene. The statement [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 641] supposes that an establishment of an ICR for *Crimes against humanity* should also links between ‘*intent*’ and ‘*act*’.

As is generally agreed and as illustrated, so far, *Crimes against humanity* connect with “*accused act*”; thus, raising further debates on whether a single act by an accused could constitute this category crimes. The American Tribunals require establishment of a massive character of a crime, while British Tribunals adopt opposite position, that the mass character of a crime does not appear essential toward either number of crimes or number of victims, but the link between act and cruel and barbarous political system; thus, specifically highlighting the Nazi regime. The issue is relevant to the discussed above terms “*widespread*” or “*systematic*” linked to ‘*attack*’; thus, highlighting that when there is established a “*widespread attack*” there is not needed to asses does the attack also appear a “*systematic*”, but the term “*systematic*” refers to ‘*plan*’.

Despite, further in this sub-section, there should be discussed the following statement:

“*[E]ven an isolated act can constitute a crime against humanity if it is the product of a political system based on terror or persecution*” [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 649].

It is based on mostly Second World War crimes and links between Collective crimes as *Crime against humanity* and *Genocide* and a *Political system*. Herein, there is reflected in mind *Formalization Policy*. Because, as is comprehensively examined over decades, a major reason for the Second World War is related with the highly centralized decision-making process in Nazi Germany^[18]; this generating "*crisis within crisis*". The Second World War itself was viewed a "*crisis*" of the German foreign policy during that time^[18]. From the perspective of the major purpose of the current study it could be emphasised on the fact that still during the Weimar Germany the socio-policy system was regarded as potentially authoritarian in power. It was granted mostly executive power authorities. For instance, the Presidency of Weimar Germany had unlimited right of dissolution of the Parliament in addition to issue Decrees; thus, avoiding engagement with Parliament over legislation. This fact causes for significant legal Decree power in the early 1930s. The Nazi German regime within 1933–1945 was only governed by decree. There was found a strong correlation between significant decreasing in number of working days of the Reichstag as well as low number of laws passed. However, there was drastically increased number of Presidential Decrees issued within the period 1930–1932.

In context of a crime categorization and definitions of crimes under Customary law, there could be added as a factual connection between *Crime against humanity* and *Genocide* committed during the Second World War as well as *Formalization Policy* of Nazi Germany the fact that still by that period, *mid*-1930s there was introduced in Germany, Austria, and Scandinavia the so-called "biologization" of "ethnolinguistic nationalism". It was adopted and developed a field of research, known as "*science of race*" (*Rassenkunde*). There was state administrators financed the research field.

Moreover, since 1913 the German citizenship law had conceived citizenship as right, or privilege, of ethnic Germans, allowing for naturalizing non-ethnic Germans only under very restricted conditions^[19].

Thus, the Nazi Germany was marginalized as a state policy so-called ethno-religious group of, for instance, Jews and Roma; homosexuals group individuals; or policy group individuals consisting of opponents of national-socialism of mostly communists and social democrats. The establishment of the network of concentration camps has been regarded as part of this program. It is implemented partially during mid-1930s and fully during the Second World War. The regime was also involved into marked expulsions of Jews and political group people of opponents from Germany and Austria still in 1938.

Particularly, the persecution of homosexual men was justified within paragraphs of criminal code (Paragraphs 175 and 175a) of the Nazi state^[20]. Such individuals, sent to concentration camps had their own pink triangle label. Convictions under Paragraph 175 are relatively well-documented. Despite, there is gap in the available literature tackling the issue.

In the field of so-called "*Research on Eastern Europe*" (*Ostforschung*) there has been highlighted a grandiose policies of racial imperialism, particularly, looking at occupied territories by Nazi Germany during 1941–1943. The segment of public German research and education had actually supported and served the Nazi machinery. There is marked professional careers development of political Nazi state disciplines including, those ones required within 1930–1940^[21].

"The existing methods and preoccupations of German Ostforschung dovetailed usefully with Nazi policy"^[21].

The role of decision-making Nazi state extermination policies could be underlined concentrating the reader's attention on Western Ukraine events during 1941–1943, where committed crimes involved a state special-action unit called *Sonderkommando*. The concept of so-called "*Slavonic-Jewish-Bolshevism*" was utilized for justifying terrorist campaign by organized Nazi groups before 1933 and by the Nazi state executives within the 1933–1945^[22,23].

The so-called "Organization Consul" during the Weimar Republic was classified as "murder commandos" ordered to "rid the German government of socialists and Jews" (p. 627)^[22]. Further, analysis has shown that military or imperial army during that time is one of many institutions expressing anti-Semitism as a cultural code.

Moreover, there is also broadly discussed the fact that the Nazi state SA executives were mostly consisted of staff turned to fascism as philosophy. They were established using mostly young men born within 1900-1908 turned to fascism and unemployed due to policy reasons after 1918 and before 1933. The novel right-wing organizations as SA offered them military service within 1933–1945^[24].

Due to these reasons the Weimar/Nazi Germany is distinguished as historical period looking at the historical development of the German socio-policy systems^[25].

However, the *Formalization Policy* of Nazi Germany is directly linked with Second World War events, including committed various category crimes.

Perhaps, due to these reasons under *Customary law*, a *Crime against humanity* is defined as:

- (a) one of a list of prohibited acts;
- (b) committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack;
- (c) pursuant to or in furtherance of a state or organizational policy;
- (d) directed against any civilian population;
- (e) with knowledge of the attack [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, §§ 639-643][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/tjug/en/tad-ts70507JT2-e.pdf>].

As can be seen, there is used word 'policy'. As an attempt to shed light on the notion the term under *Customary law* and to look at relations, sketched above, among *Formalization Policy* of Nazi Germany and post-War terminology of ICTs Statutes, there could be assumed that it refers, to *Formalization policy*.

Moreover, there is a lack of requirement for "an armed conflict". Thus, the category *Crime against humanity* under *Customary law* becomes also applicable to committed crimes during peace-time. Until the Statute for ICTY^[4], charges within category Crimes against humanity have been applied to cases of victim group of civilians under (direct) control of perpetrator; for instance, crimes committed in camps; in occupied territory during an armed conflict; within national state territory; or "Organization" supporting and conducting policy of attacking civilians. A lack of necessity of so doing has been argued for Crimes against humanity by requesting widespread or systematic attack. Thus, such crime could be committed at close quarters or at a distance. For instance, *Genocide*, was directed against Jewish people at Auschwitz as a state policy during the Second World War. Hypothetically such crimes, i.e., against an ethnic group, could be committed by weapons directed against the corresponding territory populated by the target ethnic group people. Such act; if any, however, could be a result from a state policy, but also could exclude from a state policy.

The latter statement assumes that the term "policy" under the *Customary law* rather reflects a restricted framework involving mainly collective crimes results from Formalization state policy.

From the perspective of the major purpose of this contribution, it should be further note on statement: "Where groups are mobilising without necessarily being under the direct control of the central government," there is a "grey area" between combatants and non-combatants [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 637]. It also touches upon a role of government control in armed conflicts regarding mobilising groups including troops and NSAGs.

Regarding, the definition of 'policy', there is commonly agreed that a low threshold requirement occurs. However, the current definition does not unambiguously distinguish between 'policy' in the context of Article 7(2) (a)^[1] and the term 'plan' used to tackle committed mass crimes or large scale crimes.

Focusing the reader's attention on 'plan' to carry out "attack", there should be added a set of events, *inter alia*:

- (a) the general historical circumstances and the overall political background against which the criminal acts are set;
- (b) the establishment and implementation of autonomous political structures at any level of authority in a given territory;
- (c) the general content of a political programme, as it appears in the writings and speeches of its authors;
- (d) media propaganda;
- (e) the establishment and implementation of autonomous military structures;
- (f) the mobilisation of armed forces;
- (g) temporally and geographically repeated and co-ordinated military offensives;

- (h) links between the military hierarchy and the political structure and its political programme;
- (i) alterations to the "ethnic" composition of populations;
- (j) discriminatory measures, whether administrative or other (banking restrictions, laissez-passer,...);
- (k) the scale of the acts of violence perpetrated - in particular, murders and other physical acts of violence, rape, arbitrary imprisonment, deportations and expulsions or the destruction of non-military property, in particular, sacral sites [IT-95-14-T/03.03.2000, § 204][<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2000/19490>].

Again, the role of the Formalization policy in the committed crimes is highlighted.

Looking at the latter definition used to ICTY^[4], let us try to fix connection between 'plan' and 'deportation' (point (k)), concentrating on the fact that according to ICTs the investigation is made in spite of how a crime is categorized, i.e., a crime against humanity or a war crime. Part I^[3] has attempted to detail on the latter fact; thus, providing a case example [IT-97-25-A/17.09.2003], [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/2003/en/34902>]. The content of crime deportation did not differ whether the act has been committed as a crime against humanity or war crime. The terms 'deportation' and (forcible) transfer of population are distinguished only using requirement for a case of deportation a transfer beyond a state borders [IT-98-33,02.08.2001][<https://www.icty.org/en/case/krstic>]: "...both deportation and forcible transfer relate to the involuntary and unlawful evacuation of individuals from the territory in which they reside. Yet, the two are not synonymous in customary international law. Deportation presumes transfer beyond State borders, whereas forcible transfer relates to displacements within a State"^[3]. Thus, it is clear connection between 'plane' and 'transfer' of population, as well.

In addition, link of these terms to 'attack' is underlined, above. This mutual connection among terms moves the problem of fixing a good approach to distinguish between 'plan' and 'policy'. As aforementioned, the current ambiguous definitions allow complementary employment in both the terms in categorizing *Crimes against humanity*. The group of words 'policy'-*'transfer'*-*'attack'* and 'plan'-*'transfer'*-*'attack'* are almost equally applicable, due to reasons sketched above.

What do ambiguous methods for non-strict definitions of 'plane' and 'policy' do, in fact?

Since, the category *War crimes* tackles conducts by small group individuals; for instance, a troop, consisting of mid-low level military staff, who are directly subordinate and mutually connected (Part I^[1]), a 'plan' of committing a large scale crimes involving 'transfer', which could be linked to 'attack' against civilians under Article 7^[1] could be attributed to 'policy'. Even, it could be attributed to (Formalization) State-Policy as the current study attempts to illustrate *via* a case-example, below.

However, as mentioned before, the traditional concept of the State's policy refers to crimes committed in Nazi Germany during the Second World War. Thus, it refers to Formalization policy. Both the *Crimes against humanity* and *Genocide* have collective nature and require a *State policy*, due to the fact that their commission requires employment in state's institutions, staff, and resources.

The posts Second World War ICTs adopt view that there should be applied *Customary international law*. Thus, the category *Crimes against humanity* could account for force who do not belong to legitimate government, however exercise *de facto* control over a territory, or are able to move freely within it. Although a policy must exist to commit these acts, it need not be the (Formalization) policy of a State [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §§ 654, 655][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/tjug/en/tad-ts70507JT2-e.pdf>].

In the latter context the Rome Statute^[1] states: "*an attack which is planned, directed or organized - as opposed to spontaneous or isolated acts of violence will satisfy*" the "policy" requirements of Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/05-01/08/15.06.2009, §81][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2009_04528.PDF]. The 'policy', therefore, could exclude or could not exclude from 'State', due to a lack of proper method allowing for unambiguous deciding which are the demarcation criteria on 'plane' and 'policy' as well as "policy" and Formalization 'State-Policy'.

Importantly, when one refers to a 'state' or 'organizational policy', then there is further provided examples of inconsistent case law and disagreement in specialized literature; thus, raising a crucial questions: Do non-

state perpetrators can carry out *Crimes against humanity*? This question remains still unanswered^[14]. If there is adopted the traditional view shown, above, that *Crimes against humanity* have collective nature and require a *State policy*; thus, involving state's institutions, staff, and resources as perpetrator, then, non-State perpetrators should be excluded.

It should be further said that 'State' accused could refer to "the highest level of the State machinery" or "regional" or even "local organs" of a State. Although, crimes of low-level government officials are attributable to state, frequently, there is accepted that only actors at "high level" are capable of establishing a policy. It rather reflects, however, the Formalization policy, because the discussed view agrees with work^[26] stating that Article 7(2)(a)^[1] refers to state policy. Thus, the wording "organizational policy" excludes from policy of an organization. Rather, there is reflected in mind policy of a state. Thus, it does not refer to non-state actors^[26].

Despite, case [ICC-01/05-01/08/15.06.2009, §81][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2009_04528.PDF] states that "a State or organizational policy" implies that the attack follows a regular pattern. Such a policy might be made by groups of persons who govern a specific territory or by any organization with ability to commit a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population. The policy need not be formalised. In other words, crimes and group actors should nor explicitly denote 'State'.

Work^[27] also suggests that "*Crimes against humanity*" depending on circumstances could be committed by non-State perpetrators. There could be involved actors committing crimes on behalf of a State; or, with respect to a State policy. In such cases there is introduced the concept of a "State-like Organization"; thus, attempting, for instance, to exercise territorial control or political power.

Despite the fact that there is agreed with that term "Organizational" causes for more controversy, comparing with the term 'State', there raises an important question: Under what conditions a non-state perpetrators could form an organization able to commit attack directed against any civilian population in the context of Article 7^[1].

As an attempt to shed more light on the term "Organizational", work^[27] further concentrates on dictionary definitions of organization; thus, highlighting any group of people. For instance, club, trade union, society, or business. An explicit remark on Article 7^[1], however, has been made. Article 7^[1] commonly refers to State supported atrocities.

Despite, although a policy must exist to commit these acts, it need not be the policy of a State [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §655].

At this point, there should be highlighted on the purpose of this study. Article 7^[1] rather accepts as highly theoretical "Organization" consisting of two individuals^[27].

Conversely, according to Case [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, § 48] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF] there is adopted understanding of the discussed criterion 'State' concerning "*military-like organized armed groups in the context of an armed conflict not of an international character who over a prolonged period of time allegedly committed crimes according to a policy.*"

A concept involving military-like organized armed groups or para-military units of a state in addition to organized rebel groups within a state, gangs or unorganized rebel groups into crimes under Article 7(2)(a) could be found in work^[28]. Within the framework of the term organizational policy there is include state organs, however the aforementioned groups should be extended.

If there is adopted the view that criterion 'State' involved "*military-like organized armed groups who over a prolonged period of time allegedly committed crimes against humanity*", then there is rather useful to use the term 'Plan' instead of 'Policy'. The term 'Plan' itself is more suitably attributed to 'Organization', rather than 'State', however.

Toward, "*non-military highly organized and armed groups within a state*" there is argued that non-state actors; for instance, criminal gangs frequently show a lack the mental requirement with respect to standard of 'attacking a civilian population'. They might fulfil the requirement toward 'organization'. Thus, they are subjected to jurisdiction of ICTs. Therefore, non-state perpetrators commit *crimes against humanity* depending on circumstances^[29].

At this point there should be stress on the issue of connection between law and practice of NSAGs of detention, because there is still under-regulated in international humanitarian law (IHL) and in international criminal law (ICL) the question of lawful or unlawful detention by such groups' people^[30]. The relation between IHL and international human rights is important for assessing the framework of acts defined as *Crimes against humanity* during armed conflict^[31]. The IHL formulates a set of combatants^[31]. Thus, circumstances of some crimes classified as *Crimes against humanity*, including the detention by NSAGs could be lawful and could be not explicitly clarified; thus, lacking a clearly definition. In other words, the NSAGs' authority to detain within the framework of the international law depends on States' policy, and frequently refers to domestic law defining possibility of performing lawful internment by NSAGs. A particular challenging appears the issue of detention by NSAGs in non-international armed conflicts^[30].

A Pre-Trial Chamber II agreement that non-state perpetrators could constitute an 'Organization' under Article 7(2) (a)^[31]; thus, committing *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute is detailed on, below. There has been stressed on fundamental issue related with conditions under which non-state perpetrators could satisfy the requirement for 'Organization', because of The Rome Statute is further unclear as to such criteria allowing for pursuing group who might be qualified as "Organization" for purposes of Article 7(2) (a)^[31]. Thus, only State-like organizations could be qualified, however their formal natures and level of organizations should not be defining criterion. Rather, a distinguishing criterion should be based on whether Organizations have ability of committing Crimes against humanity. [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §§ 90, 92] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

Thus, Article 7(2)(a)^[31] treat "*groups of persons who govern [de facto] a specific territory*" and "*any organisation with the capability to commit a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population*".

There is stated:

"...an organisational policy pursuant to article 7(2) (a) of the Statute ensures that the attack, even if carried out over a large geographical area or directed against a large number of victims, must still be thoroughly organised and follow a regular pattern. It must also be conducted in furtherance of a common policy involving public or private resource." [ICC-01/04-01/07/30.09.2008, § 396][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2008_05172.PDF]

In addition, there is a statement:

"The legal requisite of "multiple commission of acts" means that more than a few isolated incidents or acts as referred to in article 7(1) of the Statute have occurred. The requirement of "a State or organizational policy" implies that the attack follows a regular pattern. Such a policy may be made by groups of persons who govern a specific territory or by any organization with the capability to commit a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population. The policy need not be formalised." [ICC-01/05-01/08(15.06.2009, §81)][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2009_04528.PDF]

A particular decision also refers to factors which must be taken into considering whether a non-state perpetrator has ability to commit *Crimes against humanity*. There are shown the following criteria:

- (i) Whether the group is under a responsible command, or has an established hierarchy;
- (ii) Whether the group possesses, in fact, the means to carry out a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population;
- (iii) Whether the group exercises control over part of the territory of a State;
- (iv) Whether the group has criminal activities against the civilian population as a primary purpose;
- (v) Whether the group articulates, explicitly or implicitly, an intention to attack a civilian population;

(vi) Whether the group is part of a larger group, which fulfils some or all of the abovementioned criteria. [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §93] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

According to the latter views an 'Organization' committing crimes should exhibit a State-like nature, because of not any group having ability to commit *Crimes against humanity* could be classified as 'Organization' for purposes of Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, § 66] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

There are certain characteristics by a state-like nature of given private group:

- (a) a collectivity of persons;
- (b) which was established and acts for a common purpose;
- (c) over a prolonged period of time;
- (d) which is under responsible command or adopted a certain degree of hierarchical structure, including, as a minimum, some kind of policy level;
- (e) with the capacity to impose the policy on its members and to sanction them; and
- (f) which has the capacity and means available to attack any civilian population on a large scale.

Few Judges' statements about this issue could be considered, further.

(A) Military-like organized armed groups of armed having not of an international character who have committed crimes over a prolonged span of time;

(B) The notions 'State' and 'organization' used to purposes for 7(2)(a)^[1] do not need to constitute elements of statehood. Such 'organizations' exhibit characteristics of State.

(C) A high threshold for requirements for "organization are understood when interpreting Article 7(2)(a)[1] due to preferred avoiding of 'banalisation' or 'trivialization' of terms.

(D) The Crimes against humanity notion address "mass crimes carried out by sovereign States against civilian population. There are included cases of State's own citizens within a State plan or policy. There are involved large segments of State apparatus. It is the case when a State adopts policy to attack a civilian population; thus, causing for graves; mass crimes and victimization of the population.

In order to distinguish between international crimes and ordinary crimes punishable under domestic penal legislation, there are excludes in the former case atrocities carried out by non-state actors perpetrators group lacking of state-like nature.

An overall statement is that non-state perpetrators group having a state-like nature could satisfy the standard of 'Organization' under the Article 7(2)(a)^[1].

1.2. Standards for *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute

Since, Part II of the study, herein, attempts to relate among words; word groups or sentences and (extra)-linguistic context of terms as well as their notions which should be interpreted and applied to "do Justice" avoiding of "banalisation" or "trivialization" of them, as aforementioned, there should be stress that interpretation of sentences are primary governed by grammar rules and conventions. Therefore, there is a rather lack of significant variation of their interpretation, when there is strict defining of terms.

Despite, there have been highlighted a rather novel standards for *Crimes against humanity* looking ate cases relating to Kenya's 2008 electoral violence [Kenya; ICC-01/09/31.03.2010] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

Since, my ambition, herein, is neither to introduce, nor to define terms or requirements for various acts constituting *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute, but to highlight how over-exploring grammar of available definitions and case-statements of terms as well as "words" classifying crimes, but lacking of strict definitions could cause for confusions that tend to re-categorize crimes within AWTs^[2] due to a lack of strictly defined hypothesized crimes as well as a lack of strictly construed crimes. The latter fact assumes that AWTs^[2] are extended by analogy or they are against Article 22^[1]. This is my statement, which I attempt to argue.

Due to this reason, throughout this study I should mostly emphasis on Case [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF]. The highlights are on notional foundations of discussed so far, terms, used to define *Crimes against humanity*. On the one hand, the discussed case introduces standards of the Rome Statute^[1] of 'doing Justice' under in Article 7(2)(a)^[1], due to doubt that it, rather, re-examines common notions of these terms used to ICTs, so far. On the other hand, it involves political leaders and High State Public Elected Officials as AWTs^[2]. Particularly, it details on whether such group people has ability to commit *Crimes against humanity*. It is relevant to 'Policy' requirement under Article 7^[1]. Furthermore, there is commented on case tackling policies to attack a civilian population in a so diverse context, so that there is excluded from operating with one common understanding in dealing with 'Policy' requirement.

Despite the fact that the discussed case treats 272 persons died and 52 611 burnt houses, there are cases of 21 749 displaced people due to violence within the period 12.2007–02.2008 as result from Presidential election in December 2007 in Republic of Kenya [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §87] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF]. Its content is directly relevant with AWTs^[2] wording highlighting 'deportation' and 'transfer' of civilian people.

First, a Judge statement rejects this criterion. There is argued that only organizations having a "state-like" nature could satisfy Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, § 66] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

Under the Article 7(2)(a)^[1] as mentioned in the preceding sub-sections there is debatable whether non-state perpetrators could adopt any policy within the notion of the term used to ICTY^[4] or International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR)^[32] owing to the fact that there is not explicitly entailed such requirement in defining *Crimes against humanity*^[33]. The Rome Statute, however, entails 'Policy' as such as requirement. A common statement is that the latter standard should be seen apart from customary law. Despite, Pre-Trial Chamber II of the discussed in this sub-section case have been divided on the issue whether Article 7(2) (a)^[1] should be interpreted and applied in light of ICTs practice, so far. Therefore, there is disagreement regarding charges under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] comparing to customary law. Importantly, the Rome Statute does not in-depth clarify the notion 'Policy' and how the policy standard should be understood and applied to Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. Thus, there have been detailed on definition of concept in ICTs by some Judges [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §86] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

Conversely, a Judge argues that the Statutes of both the ICTY^[4] and ICTR^[??] do not contain equivalent legal standard to that of Article 7(2)(a)^[1] toward the term "State or organizational policy". The "Policy" is not a legal standard. However, it might have evidential relevance for crimes in the context of "attack" against the civilian population. The Article 7(2)(a)^[1] is "not limited to the question of whether a systematic attack has taken place, but rather "a legal requirement radiating on the entire chapeau of Article 7 of the Statute as it is linked with the element of 'attack' and not the component 'systematic'" [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §§ 30–32] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF]. In other words, the latter statement rather links terms "Policy" and "State or organizational policy" with mostly "Attack" in a rather common context under the entire Article 7^[1].

Despite, the variation of Judges' statements raises a specific question: Should standards for 'State' or 'Organizational policy' be independent contextual ones or they rather only support for establishing the "systematic" nature of an "Attack" (against civilians) as required by Article 7(1)^[1]?

The discussion on the issue involves a set of opinions some of which follows the ICTY^[4] practice stating:

"[N]either the attack nor the acts of the accused needs to be supported by any form of "policy" or "plan". There was nothing in the Statute or in customary international law at the time of the alleged acts which required proof of the existence of a plan or policy to commit these crimes...[P]roof that the attack was directed against a civilian population and that it was widespread or systematic, are legal elements of the crime. But to prove these elements, it is not necessary to show that they were the result of the existence of a

policy or plan. It may be useful in establishing that the attack was directed against a civilian population and that it was widespread or systematic (especially the latter) to show that there was in fact a policy or plan, but it may be possible to prove these things by reference to other matters. Thus, the existence of a policy or plan may be evidentially relevant, but it is not a legal element of the crime” (consider [IT-96-23-T & IT-96-23/1-T, 12.06.2002, §98][<https://cld.irmct.org/assets/filings/Judgement-Kunarac.pdf>]). Case [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §653][<https://www.icty.org/x/cases/tadic/tjug/en/tad-ts70507JT2-e.pdf>] underlines that some form of policy is required for constituting *Crimes against humanity*. In this case, when crimes occur on a widespread or systematic manner that there could be supposed a policy causing for committing such acts, in spite of its formal character or not. At this point, it could be mentioned that the word ‘Policy’ has been used rather in context ‘plan’.

In parallel, there is also stated:

“...Only the attack not the individual acts of the accused must be widespread or systematic” [IT-96-23-T & IT-96-23/1-T, 12.06.2002, §96][<https://cld.irmct.org/assets/filings/Judgement-Kunarac.pdf>]. The latter statement assumes that “Policy” and “State or organizational policy”; if any, could not be linked only with “Attack”, but the nature of the attack should be compulsorily established as “widespread” or “systematic” one.

Despite, there are defined five key elements inherent in *Crimes against humanity* under the RS^[1]:

“(i) An attack directed against any civilian population,
(ii) a State or organizational policy,
(iii) the widespread or systematic nature of the attack,
(iv) a nexus between the individual act and the attack, and
(v) knowledge of the attack.” [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §79] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF]

Thus, majority of Judges in Pre-Trial Chambers II/III of the case above link the terms “State” or “Organizational policy” to standard for “systematic attack”. There has been argued that the relevant criteria to qualify an “Organization” under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] involved “whether such group individuals have ability to do widespread or systematic attack. The latter statement bridges the Rome Statute^[1] and the Statute for ICTY^[4], particularly Case [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §653] stating that if there are crimes on a widespread or systematic manner, than this fact demonstrates a rather policy, whether Formalization policy or not [<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/1997/40193>].

Since, the Case [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §653] refers to [Article 6(c) of the Nürnberg Charter] stating that:

“The concept of ‘crimes against humanity’ also requires - although this is not expressed in so many words in the above definition [Article 6(c) of the Nürnberg Charter] - that the crimes in question form a part of a system based on terror or constitute a link in a consciously pursued policy directed against particular groups of people” [IT-94-1-T/07.05.1997, §653][<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/1997/40193>], then owing to the traditional concept of *State policy*, mentioned before, and employing state’s institutions, staff, and resources, then the link between the two Statutes which the Pre-Trial Chamber II have made does not exclude from formalization “policy”. In other words, the majority Judges in Pre-Trial Chamber II do agree a lack of fundamental difference in Rome Statute and the customary law. The extension of this understanding implies that when an Organized group people has conducted a “systematic attack”, then there could be evidenced an organizational policy.

As aforementioned, there is also a distinct Judge opinion arguing that the standards for Article 7(2)(a)^[1] under the Rome Statute are distinctly different from the customary law ones; thus, adding at extra elements regarding terms “State” or “Organizational policy” and linking mostly to “attack” itself, rather than to its “widespread” or “systematic” nature.

Due to these reasons the following two sub-sections shed more light how the variations of Judge opinions affects on other important terms and issues regarding *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute and treating cases involving political leaders and High State Public Elected Officials.

1.2. 1. The "Orange Democratic Movement" case

It involves Minister of Higher Education (MHE); former Minister of Industrialization (MI) and radio presenter (RP) [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.10.2010, §§1, 37, 41, 43] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2012_03827.PDF].

MHE and MI planned for attacking political party oppositionists as an attempt to punish and expel them from the electoral region; thus, gaining officially elected political power in the corresponding province. Due to lost of policy support and ICC-01/09-01/11/15.10.2010 on December 30, 2007 as established by the National Electoral Commission the "Organized group" established by MHE and MI has been activated to kill and oppress opposition supporters on different locations in the province. The by the "Organization" committed crimes involve persecution, torture, murder, deportation or forcible transfer of opposition supporters.

There has been found reasonable grounds to believe that MHE and MI are criminally responsible as indirect co-perpetrators of Crimes against humanity under Article 25(3)(a)^[1].

The RP has been found responsible for contributing in other manner to the commission of the crimes against humanity under Article 25(3)(d)^[1].

There is argued that MHE, MI, and RP had "coordinated a series of actors and institutions to establish a network, using it to implement an organizational policy to commit crimes" [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.10.2010, §1].

The highlighted "network" involves media representatives as RP among others, regional tribal Elders, financiers, and former staff and leaders of Kenya's security apparatus; thus, classifying the network as "Organization" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.10.2010, §19].

The majority of Judges agreed with presence of a state or organizational policy to commit such attack [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.10.2010, §20].

Despite, an opposed Judge's statement argued for a lack of fulfilled requirements of Article 7(2) (a)^[1]. In other words the standards have not been met [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.03.2011, §2], At this point, there should be stress on the fact that the Judge opinion and application of Article7(2)(a)^[1] potentially determine whether any of the accused individuals are charged and further convicted for *Crimes against humanity*. The Article 7(2) (a)^[1] classifies the crime events as a crime against humanity [ICC-01/09-01/11-373/23.01.2012, §59] and [ICC-01/09-02/11-382/23.01.2012, §65][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2012_01004.PDF]. The interpretation of Article 7(2)(a)^[1] might affect on outcome of a Trial depending on the evidence does not meet the higher threshold standard under Article 61(7)^[1].

Article 61(7)^[1]

(Confirmation of the charges before trial)

(7) The Pre-Trial Chamber shall, on the basis of the hearing, determine whether there is sufficient evidence to establish substantial grounds to believe that the person committed each of the crimes charged. Based on its determination, the Pre-Trial Chamber shall....

In considering does "network" establish should be understood as an "Organization" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1], there have been highlighted the following criteria causing for reasonable grounds to believe that it could be classified as "Organization":

- (i) [It was] "under responsible command;
- (ii) had "an established hierarchy;
- (iii) possessed the means to carry out a widespread or systematic attack against the civilian population;

(iv) identified the criminal activities against the civilian population as its primary purpose; and articulated an intention to attack the civilian population.

As a major motivation behind point (iii) has been highlighted the fact that the network's members had access to and utilised a considerable amount of capital, guns, crude weapons and manpower. Thus, the network had ability to commit crimes against humanity and it constituted an "Organization" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1].

Toward establishing requirements to "Policy" by the network, there has been only noted that *"there are reasonable grounds to believe that the organization promoted a policy aimed at targeting members of the civilian population"*. Within such policy there is mechanism to motivate perpetrators to commit a large scale crimes including killing of population.

A separate Judge's statement provide different tool for tackling the issue whether the network in the "Orange Democratic Movement" case could be regarded as "Organization". There are analyzed each of the five branches, branch-by-branch, i.e., the political one; the media branch; the financial branch; the tribal one; and the military branches, respectively. The major Judge's statement refers to the so-called tribal branch. It has been understood as composed elders and had played a pivotal role in the violence [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.03.2011, §§42–46].

The established a lack of a hierarchy among the network's branches assumes a "a horizontal level" coordination of activities. It is regarded as *"a substitute for the prerequisite of 'responsible command' within a vertical hierarchical structure."*

Further feature concentrates on *"its [of the network] temporary existence for a specific purpose."*: *"[T]he 'Network' was created ad hoc solely to assist, admittedly in an abhorrent way, the community's aspiring and existing political leaders in gaining or maintaining political power in the Rift Valley on the occasion of the 2007 presidential elections"*.

Due to these reasons the network had not been assigned by the Judge to a state-like organization under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/09-01/11/15.03.2011, §47].

Despite, there has been accepted that there had been a *"group of perpetrators with a pre-disposition to violence engaged in a regional campaign of aggressive inter-ethnic violence, at the instigation of those persons within their tribe who were seeking to achieve their political aims at all costs"*.

The majority of Judges have qualified it as "Organization" Article 7(2)(a)^[1] without much detail on; thus, further accepting that it promoted a policy against a target members of civilian population.

1.2.2. The "Party of National Unity" case

The second case is closely connected with the former one and involves supporters of a party presidential campaign and/or government officials, i.e., Head of Public Services (HPS); Minister for Finance (MF), and Head of Kenya's Police Forces (KPF) [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.12.2010, §§ 5, 37, 43, 47][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2012_03828.PDF]. It deals with violence launched by "Orange Democratic Movement" supporters; thus, aiming at keeping the "Party of National Unity" in power. The HPS and KPF used their State' authority positions in the National Security Advisory Committee to order the Kenyan Police Forces to apply excessive violence to opposition party supporters. In addition, there is involved a "criminal gang" attacking against civilian population or "Orange Democratic Movement" supporters. The "criminal gang" has been described as complex, multi-faceted, heterogeneous and decentralized" criminal structure consisting of local and regional branches [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.12.2010, §19][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

The HPS and KPS mutually coordinated to ensure a lack of the police interference with the planned attacks by the criminal gang. The MF had provided financial and logistical support for the plan. The committed crimes also involve rape, murder, other sexual violence, persecution, deportation or forcible transfer of population [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.12.2010, §30][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

“For their part, the Kenyan Police Forces are an integral part of the State apparatus with a hierarchy and a chain of command. The evidence tends to show that [HPS] and [KPF] are de jure and de facto responsible for the policies, operations and actions of the Kenyan Police” [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.12.2010, §30].

“The HPS was chairman of the National Security Advisory Committee and “exercised both de jure and de facto authority over the various Kenyan security agencies, including the Kenya Police, Administration Police and the National Security and Intelligence Service”. He [KPF] was under the direct authority of [HPS] and routinely reported to him” [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011 §18][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

HSP and KPF have utilized the Kenyan Police Force to perpetrate attacks by (1) directing the Kenyan Police Forces to target perceived “Orange Democratic Movement” supporters in attacks; and (2) directing them not to intervene in attacks by the “criminal gang” against perceived “Orange Democratic Movement” supporters [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011 §22][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

The Pre-Trial Chamber II decision details on, among others:

Deportation or forcible transfer of population constituting a crime against humanity under Article 7(1)(d)^[1] and Article 25(3)(a)^[1] or Article 25(3)(d)^[1] due to that from on or about 27.12.2007 to 29.02.2008, HPS, MF, and KPF as co-perpetrators, or in the alternative, as part of a group of persons acting with a common purpose, committed or contributed to the commission of crimes against humanity, namely the deportation or forcible transfer of civilian population supporting the Orange Democratic Movement political party in or around locations [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011][https://www.worldcourts.com/icc/eng/decisions/2011.03.08_Prosecutor_v_Muthaura.pdf].

Other inhumane acts constituting a crime against humanity under Articles 7(1)(k)^[1], and Article 25(3)(a)^[1] or Article 25(3)(d)^[1] by HPS, MF, and KPF as co-perpetrators or in the alternative, as part of same group over same period [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011][https://www.worldcourts.com/icc/eng/decisions/2011.03.08_Prosecutor_v_Muthaura.pdf].

There has been found a reasonable believe that MF and HPS are responsible as indirect co-perpetrators under Article 25(3)(a)^[1], while KPF is responsible for having otherwise contributed to the commission of crimes under Article 25(3)(d)^[1][ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §49]. MF has been highlighted as principal contact person between the “criminal gang” and the Principal Perpetrators [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.12.2010, §31].

Importantly, there have been found reasonable believes that the “criminal gang” has committed crimes against humanity [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §§25–28].

In addition, the investigated cases of police inaction or police shootings do not meet the standard for Crimes against humanity [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §§24, 31, 32]. The three Judges have argued that these acts could not be attributed to an organizational policy, despite, the prosecutor statement; thus, declining to include them. There has not been provided further explanation regarding that crimes carried out by state agencies, including the police inaction. The act or inact are not examined they are part of an organizational policy. Thus, the police inaction during the committed crimes has been excluded from the case against the HPS, MF, and KPF [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §20]. The same is valid to cases of Police shootings which have been excluded from the examining of the widespread or systematic nature of the attack against the civilian population, despite that within the period 12.2007–01.2008 the Police officers have used excessive force causing for 60 deaths in addition to other activities promoting other inhumane acts constituting a crime against humanity as injuries and rapes [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §30]. According to the Chamber these crimes do not fall under the Rome Statute and do not meet the

requirements in Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. The major motivation behind the latter decision has been that there is insufficient evidence that the police shooting could be attributed to HPS, MF, and KPF as suspects. Despite, there has been written the Judge statement that Article 7(2)(a)^[1] should be understood in the context that state actors, including the police, cannot be agents of an organizational policy.

The "Policy" requirement under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] has been detailed on the "criminal gang", among others. A Judge statements argues for a lacking of meeting threshold criteria on an "Organization". Despite, the Prosecutor has insisted in existence of a policy, as far as the three suspects "adopted and implemented a common plan. There has not been specified does the criminal gang as relevant entity is tackled as organization. In addition, there is a lack of specifying whether the term "Organization" should be understood broadly; thus, involving Kenyan Police Forces and/or the National Security Advisory Committee, as well.

In both the case of **sub-sections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2** there is separate assessments of whether an "Organization" under Article 7(2)(a) has been established and whether a 'Policy' has been adopted. For the purpose of this study, I shall focus the reader attention on the "criminal gang" involved into committing *Crimes against humanity*. It has been found that "criminal gang" has complex and large hierarchical structure, consisting of different levels of command. In addition there is underlined division of duties within the framework of the command structure. Further, there are strict disciplinary measures and internal rules. Thus, there is assessed the responsible command level and the hierarchy. In addition, it involves trained militant wing used to perform violence, including executions. The conclusion is that the "criminal gang" has ability to commit widespread or systematic attack. Moreover, the "criminal gang" also: (i) control and provide social services such as electricity, water and sanitation; (ii) administer criminal justice through local chairmen who act as judges in their communities; and (iii) control the transport sector and other business activities, where they provide informal employment for members [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §22].

Particularly, a Judge statement says:

"I read [article 7(2)(a) of the Statute] such that the juxtaposition of the notions "State" and 'organization' in article 7(2)(a) of the Statute are an indication that even though the constitutive elements of statehood need not be established those 'organizations' should partake of some characteristics of a State. Those characteristics eventually turn the private 'organization' into an entity which may act like a State or has quasi-State abilities. These characteristics could involve the following:

- (a) a collectivity of persons;*
- (b) which was established and acts for a common purpose;*
- (c) over a prolonged period of time;*
- (d) which is under responsible command or adopted a certain degree of hierarchical structure, including, as a minimum, some kind of policy level;*
- (e) with the capacity to impose the policy on its members and to sanction them; and*
- (f) which has the capacity and means available to attack any civilian population on a large scale"* [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §12][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

Despite, there has been remarked on a lack of clear how these remarks would support of these findings for the five established and aforementioned criteria on determining whether such group has the ability to carry out Crimes against humanity. Some of the activities of the "criminal gang" seems to contravene the basic criterion that *"the group has criminal activities against the civilian population as a primary purpose"*. It is further remarked on the doubt that this is a specific case when there is believed that "the group articulates, explicitly or implicitly, an intention to attack a civilian population" is fulfilled in the context of the standard criterion on this category crimes [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, § 93] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF].

A conclusion has been drawn: "In light of the foregoing, the Chamber is of the opinion that the material submitted provides reasonable grounds to believe that the ["criminal gang"] is qualifying as an organization

within the meaning and for the purposes of Article 7(2) (a) of the Statute" [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §22].

Further, within the "Policy" requirement in Article 7(2)(a) there is adopted the view that "attack in some locations has been performed due to policy established by the "criminal gang". This conclusion has been reached on evidence that it ["criminal gang"] is involved into planning of meetings; attackers from elsewhere to the location of the attacks; distributing "large quantities of crude weapons to the attackers; and circulated leaflets announcing the attacks among the targeted population. Despite, the fact that the "criminal gang" is a separate structural unity its crimes are examined together within the discussed case, because of there is established that the common policy of one organization under Article 7(2)(a)^[1] in this case includes the "criminal gang's one.

Moreover, the "criminal gang" appears to have significant benefited from financial and other support from 'Party of National Unity' politicians [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §29][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

The same has been stated looking at events associated with Kenyan Police Forces, other politicians of the "Party of National Unity", in addition to "Party of National Unity" supporters, because of the prosecutor initially elaborates on view that the "Organization", includes the Police, the criminal gang, state and non-state actors. The "criminal gang", itself, however, is seen as an organization under Article 7(2)(a)^[1][ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §§25,26], because of the "criminal gang" has established "parallel structures in poorer parts of the country lacking of effective State authority. Furthermore, the region shows in the past a certain degree of political flexibility; thus, supporting various political parties in order to advance its own regional interests. Despite, a Judge statements refers on connection between the 'criminal gang" and the Kenyan police forces of the region but excludes from both of them as primary perpetrators of crimes under Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. Rather, there is proposed "cooperation" between the 'criminal gang" and the Kenyan Police Forces having ad hoc nature; thus, excluding from a determined common "Organization" consisting mainly of 'criminal gang" and Kenyan Police Forces population [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §31][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

Due to reasons sketched above criminal activities of state perpetrators are on a rather private basis, instead of according to a policy of the state as such [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §12][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

The latter statement framed a common view that there should be distinguished among the various category crimes in addition to international crimes and common crimes, albeit their serious character.

"[A] demarcation line must be drawn between international crimes and human rights infractions; between international crimes and ordinary crimes; between those crimes subject to international jurisdiction and those punishable under domestic penal legislation"[ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011, §4][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF].

Regarding the fact that both the cases discussed in **sub-sections 1.2.1** and **1.2.2** involve "deportation" or "forcible transfer" of civilian population [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011][https://www.worldcourts.com/icc/eng/decisions/2011.03.08_Prosecutor_v_Muthaura.pdf], which in the latter case have been carried out mostly by a "criminal gang" recognized as "Organization" under Article 7(2)(a)^[1], and the discussed "criminal gang" exhibits characteristics of NSAGs as discussed in work^[30], at this point there could be added the Macro Case 01 tackling various types of detention. The civilians in the latter case are mostly used for purposes of an exchange with imprisoned guerrillas^[30]. However, many acts have been also classified as kidnapping^[30].

Particularly, the link between the "Party of National Unity" case and Macro Case 01^[30] is due to the fact that the "criminal gang" in the former case (i) controls and provides social services such as electricity, water and sanitation, among other services [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §22]; thus, supposing that the cases of deportation or forcible transfer could be associated with humane treatment of the population due to

temporal circumstances and events involving the period of Presidential election 2007–2008, due to obligation to provide humane treatment. It is independent of the non- or lawful nature of the detention^[30].

Owing to the fact that Macro Case 01 deals with kidnapping during armed conflict; thus, classifying the crime of detention or kidnapping as War crime under Article 8(2)(iii)^{[1][30]}, there should be added that there is a lack of clear understanding when a detention by NSAGs is lawful or it is always within the framework of an non-international armed conflict^[30]. Does the events treated within the framework of the “*Party of National Unity*” case can be regarded as non-international armed conflict owing to the fact that, on the one hand, there is involved a distinct armed “criminal gang” classified as Organization under Article 7(2)(a)^[1]. On the other hand, there are different armed Kenyan security agencies, including the Kenya Police, Administration Police and the National Security and Intelligence Service [ICC-01/09-02/11/15.03.2011 §18][https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2011_02712.PDF]. In parallel, there is an armed network within the “*Orange Democratic Movement*” case; thus, supposing a local domestic non-international armed conflict, as well. The latter issue is raised due to the common understanding that Crimes against humanity must be carried within the framework of an armed conflict, whether international or internal-one^[13]. The same is valid to category War crimes; thus, arguing that certain crimes are apply to armed conflicts in spite of their classification^[13].

The parallel analysis of different cases involving the same type crime committed due to various circumstances is of significant importance for a comprehensive understanding of the mechanism of “*doing Justice*” due to the constant concerns of whether or not a arrest warrant could be extended to cover the charge of various crimes under Articles 6^[1], Articles 7^[1], and Articles 8^[1] [ICC-02/05-01/09-73/03.02.2010]^[34].

Moreover, the Prosecutors are expected to ‘pay attention to all relevant circumstances, irrespective of whether they are to the advantage or disadvantage of the suspect^[35].

When we turn from the cases used as examples detailing on the standards for *Crimes against humanity* under the Rome Statute in **sub-section 1.2** to the major purpose of this study, we could again fix on the fact that application of both the Article 25(3)(a)^[1] and Article 25(3)(b)^[1] involves superiors- subordinate mutual relations determined within the framework of effective control and authority of superiors (consider the examples provided to Part I^[3]). As the preceding paragraphs show such relations have been also established examining the “criminal gang” governing its activity *via* duties and obligations within the framework of the command structure [ICC-01/09-02/11/08.03.2011, §22].

2. Concepts of Individual criminal responsibility connected with *Crimes against humanity* and the arrest warrants wording

To begin with, herein, I would like to refer back to various doctrines developed and used to primary tool for and mechanism seeking ICR by superiors for “*failing to prevent*” or “*punish crimes*” committed by their subordinates; thus, making still at this point a remark on that “subordinates” should be under direct command/authority as well as direct and effective control by the “superiors”.

The doctrine of *superior or command responsibility* is highlighted as a major concept and important tool, among others, in punishing individuals, occupying superior positions for their lacking of control, respectively, supervision over their subordinates. As Part I^[1] has attempted to highlight, it is developed for examining relations among mid-low militaries group individuals consisting of mostly troops who are mutually and directly in subordinate relationships.

Further, herein, there should be added the JCE doctrine, among others, or the so-called common purpose liability doctrine; thus, linking to ICTY^[4] Statute. Because, on the one hand it has become tool for prosecuting high, respectively, senior government officials; for instance, case [IT-02-54] or [IT-00-39 and 40/1]. On the other hand, as mentioned in preceding sub-sections concept of co-perpetration under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] links rather to JCE, instead of to CC doctrine^[16]. The superior-subordinates relations are a primary basis of seeking liability. Particularly, case [IT-02-54] applies JCE as primary mode of seeking liability, but as aforementioned it fails to punish reliably; thus, involving innocence individual into the full scale of liability modes under ICTY^[4] Statute^[36].

Owing to the fact that, the term “attack” on civilians are Violation of the Laws or Customs of War under Article 51 of Additional Protocol I and Article 13 of Additional Protocol II to Geneva Conventions of 1949 and it punishable under Article 7(1)^[4] and Article 7(3)^[4]; and, “*unlawful attacks against civilians*” is same in both the internal- and internal conflicts, but the Rome Statute^[1] does not explicitly clarify terms as “*widespread*” or “*systematic*” requested for examining *Crimes against humanity* elements. Moreover, there is a lack of clear demarcation line between terms ‘plan’ and ‘policy’, in spite, of the fact that the term “*systematic*” involves ‘plan’. However, when there is established a “ *widespread attack*” there is not needed to establish further a “ *systematic attack*’ nature of same crime.

Furthermore, as preceding sub-sections already has shown a Judge opinion states that the Rome Statute does not in-depth clarify the term ‘policy’ and how it standard should be understood and applied to Article 7(2)(a)^[1] [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §86] [https://www.icc-cpi.int/sites/default/files/CourtRecords/CR2010_02409.PDF]. Due to these reasons there have been detailed on definition of concept in ICTs by some Judges [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010]; thus, linking cases under RS^[1] with ICTs Statutes, particularly tackling conducts by high, respectively, senior government officials. In the latter context, the superior responsibility doctrines are primary used to punish “inactivity”. In seeking superior responsibility a (non-)military superior could be punished for a failure to act.

Within the liability theory there is the following governing rule:

“*[W]e must accept the principle that he who knows of a crime, and is able and bound to prevent it but fails to do so, himself commits a crime.*”^[37]. The latter statement captures superior responsibility doctrine, in fact^[37].

However, there are implemented a *functional aspect* detailing on a concept of that a superior position must entail a duty to act. In addition, there is a *cognitive element*, accounting for a concept that a superior “must have known” or “should have known” of conducts committed by his, respectively, her subordinates. Further, there is an *operational element* looking at the concept of that a superior must have failed to act. These aspects are encapsulated in Article 86 of Additional Protocol I (AP I) to the 1949 Geneva Conventions [x5]; thus, linking the notion of terms understood within the framework of the Customary Law. For instance, the term ‘policy’ which should be detailed on in this subsection looking at AWTs^[2].

Commonly, the “failure to act” could involve (i) one *knew*, or *had reason to know*, that the acts were about to be carried out and failed to prevent such conducts. It could also involve (ii) one did not *know* of acts being carried out, but once informed, he, respectively, she failed to punish them and/or report such crimes to proper authorities. Thus, there are accepted the so-called “pre-crime” and “post-crime” events of the superior responsibility. A common understanding is that only “post-crime” events only yield to *superior responsibility*, i.e., the aspects included in point (ii). Due to these reasons, superior-subordinate relations are governed by direct and effective command and control, respectively, authority at the time of the offence [IT-01-47-AR72/16.07.2003][<https://ucr.irmct.org/scasedocs/case/IT-01-47>].

Since, the term “*effective control*” is a key aspect of the doctrine of superior responsibility, there is agreed with that only when a superior exercises effective *de facto* or *de jure* control as commander/superior be held liable for acts carried out by subordinates. The term “control” is determined in the NATO glossary as “authority exercised by a commander over part of the activities of subordinate organizations, or other organizations not normally under his command, which encompasses the responsibility for implementing orders or directives. All or part of this authority may be transferred or delegated.” [NATO Glossary of Terms and Definitions, AAP-6-2009, available at <http://www.nato.int/docu/stanag/aap006/aap-6-2009.pdf>.]

There could be further added that:

“*[w]here a commander exercises executive power over occupied territory, he is responsible for the acts committed within that area of responsibility regardless of whether a unit is subordinated to his command or not. As the commander bearing executive power, he is charged with responsibility for maintaining peace and order within the area over which his executive authority extends, and the duty of crime prevention rests upon him*”^[38].

The close link between superiors and subordinates makes the doctrine (superior responsibility) inapplicable to seek liability mode for individuals at the top end of the hierarchy. In other words, it is inapplicable to superiors who are far removed from the crime scene and who cannot be directly linked to the corresponding perpetrators (subordinates) committing a crime. Therefore, it is unsuitable for senior superiors^[39]. Despite the fact that the “control” is a tool for evaluating a commander’s responsibility for (military) units or organizations not normally under his command, and it is the key aspect in establishing the de facto superior responsibility of non-military superiors, there should be stress on the statement that:

“[T]he doctrine of superior responsibility extends to civilian superiors only to the extent that they exercise a degree of control over their subordinates which is similar to that of military commanders.” [IT-96-21-T/16.11.1998, §346][<https://www.refworld.org/jurisprudence/caselaw/icty/1998/91857>]. The Paragraph defines the essential elements of the *command responsibility* doctrine. It states:

[E]ssential elements of command responsibility for failure to act as follows:

- (i) the existence of a superior-subordinate relationship;
- (ii) the superior knew or had reason to know that the criminal act was about to be or had been committed; and
- (iii) the superior failed to take the necessary and reasonable measures to prevent the criminal act or punish the perpetrator thereof.

Therefore, position *de facto* or *de jure* of command commonly imposed military-disciplinary responsibility. There are only, few cases did it entail individual criminal responsibility. As aforementioned, one of which [IT-02-54] involves inane individual occupying senior government official position.

A remark on the latter context is that within the theory of the superior order there is duty and right of a subordinate to refuse to obey. If the theory of the superior order is applied to military-disciplinary organizations, then it should be extended to *superior-subordinate* relations tackling civilian subordinate, as well.

In other words, the developed doctrines seeking mode of liability within the superior-subordinate relationships are designed and mostly used to mid-low militaries group individuals as troops who are mutually directly subordinate linked to a (similar to) military commander orders are obviously inapplicable to the case of **Subject 1** and AWT^[2]. Moreover, the “*should have known*” standard is codified in Article 28(i)(a)^[1] as the cognitive standard for military superiors, however. Since, as aforementioned, the cognitive element of the collective crimes is directly connected with a very complex and disputable term ‘knowledge’, my further study should detail on how it is unreliably implemented into AWTs^[2].

However, in what follows I would like to concentrate the reader’s attention on further on Article 25(3)(a). As provided case-examples of Part I^[3] and cases discussed in preceding sub-sections and involving accused charged under Article 25(3)(a)^[1] as high state individuals, there has been unambiguous pro-argued for the statement for a complete inapplicability of Article 25(3)(a)^[1] to Subject 1 case and AWTs^[2].

Because, with respect to hypothesized *War crimes* within the AWTs^[2] and relating to deportation of Ukrainian (!) children to Russia, which is broadly attached to **Subject 1**; furthermore, as Individual criminal responsibility^[40] both the publicly and legally^[2], herein, I would like to concentrate the reader’s attention on Judgement by The Grand Chamber of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) in Strasbourg looking at Case Ukraine and the Netherlands v. Russia; 9 July 2025 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22itemid%22:%5B%22002-14493%22%5D%7D>]; thus, shaping a connection of the term “deportation” with the term “policy”.

The motivation behind this analysis I have attempted to sketch; I hope successfully in the preceding sub-sections of this study, but mostly it is based on the statements that; (i) “*The legal requisite of “multiple commission of acts” means that more than a few isolated incidents or acts as referred to in article 7(1) of*

the Statute have occurred. The requirement of "a State or organizational policy" implies that the attack follows a regular pattern. Such a policy may be made by groups of persons who govern a specific territory or by any organization with the capability to commit a widespread or systematic attack against a civilian population. The policy need not be formalised." [ICC-01/05-01/08(15.06.2009, §81); and (ii) "[E]ven an isolated act can constitute a crime against humanity if it is the product of a political system based on terror or persecution" [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 649]; thus, tackling the issue that there could be seek connection between category *crime against humanity* and the *political system*. Due to these reasons, herein, I would like to concentrate on the term *Formalization Policy*, and how it could be linked, but again wrongly, to events of 'deportation' and 'transfer' of children; if any, from Ukraine to the Russia Federation. Why wrongly?

The latter question is addressed looking at the law- and decision-making mechanisms of the socio-political system of the Russian Federation, described from the perspective of the text of the Case Ukraine and the Netherlands v. Russia; 9 July 2025 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%22itemid%22:%22002-14493%22>]] and the dimension of the effective power authority of the Presidency of the Russian Federation.

Thus, case "*Ukraine and the Netherlands v. Russia*"/09.07.2025 implemented four cases, in fact, *i.e.*, 8019/16, 43800/14, 28525/20, and 11055/22. For the purpose of this study, the reader's attention is focused only on case 43800/14 (hereafter **EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025**) (consider Judgment 9.7.2025 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%22itemid%22:%22002-14493%22>]]))

According to Decision on 30.11.2020 [<https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%22itemid%22:%22001-222889%22>]], the case EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025 refers to "*abduction*" and "*transfer*" to Russia of three groups of children (no. 43800/14). The applicant is the Ukrainian Government.

There is stated:

"The applicant Ukrainian Government maintained that the three groups of children had been abducted and referred to the evidence that they had provided in this respect" [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025; §894].

Further:

*"The Court notes that the applicant Ukrainian Government invoked **three incidents**, each involving the alleged **abduction of a group of children and accompanying adults**, which occurred over a period of around **two and a half months in the summer of 2014**. A total of **85 children without parental care were allegedly abducted and transferred to Russia** in the course of these incidents. The Court notes the very young age of many of the children concerned: the material before the Court indicates that **the vast majority of the children in the second group were under the age of five years old** and that **all of the children in the third group were two years old or younger**. Moreover, **the third group of children included six infants with cerebral palsy** (see paragraphs 95-96 above). The Court is satisfied that in the circumstances of the present case, notably the short period of time within which these three events occurred and the number and characteristics of the children involved, these incidents may be deemed sufficiently numerous to amount to a pattern or system (compare and contrast *Ukraine v. Russia (re. Crimea)*, cited above, § 399). In consequence, the required standard of proof has been met in respect of the alleged repetition of the acts for the purposes of establishing an administrative practice. Moreover, for the reasons outlined above (see paragraph 883-888), there is also sufficiently substantiated *prima facie* evidence of official tolerance in respect of these complaints"* [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §896].

*"It is not disputed that the three groups of children and accompanying adults **concerned crossed the border and entered the Russian Federation**. However, the material before the Court demonstrates a fundamental disagreement between the parties as to **whether the crossings were voluntary or involuntarily**. In view of the material supplied by the applicant Ukrainian Government, the Court is satisfied that they have discharged the burden of proof incumbent on them at this stage of the proceedings of showing sufficiently substantiated *prima facie* evidence of the complaints under Article 5 and Article 2 of Protocol No. 4 that **the transfer to and crossing of the border were involuntary and occurred with the intervention of armed separatists**. It is moreover satisfied that this threshold has been overcome in respect of the complaints*

under Articles 3 and 8 having regard to the young age of the individuals concerned and the special health needs of at least one of the groups of children. It will be for the Court at the merits stage to decide whether the material provided by the applicant Ukrainian Government is sufficient to overcome the threshold of beyond reasonable doubt in respect of each of the complaints advanced when confronted with the evidence supplied by the respondent State” [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §897].

“The applicant Ukrainian Government’s complaint of an administrative practice in violation of Articles 3, 5 and 8 of the Convention and Article 2 of Protocol No. 4 to the Convention in respect of the alleged abduction of three groups of children is accordingly declared admissible” [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §898].

Thus, there are defined three (3) group’s children:

Group 1: Children without parental case;

Group 2: Very young children below five (5) years old; and

Group 3: Six (6) infants with cerebral palsy.

In total, there 85 children [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §896].

Looking at the text of Paragraphs [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025; §§896–898], I would like to mention that Part I^[3] explicitly details on terms ‘deportation’ and ‘state border’. Owing to the fact that there is a lack of strict time framework of the discussed three (3) events, but is only written “two and a half months in the summer of 2014”, I would like to emphasised on the two facts that: (i) For such events; if any, and dating before 24.02.2022, a responsibility should be examined within the Army of the Russian Federation or the Russian Border Control Authority in addition to Ukrainian Border Control Authority or Donetsk, respectively, Luhansk Republics Control Authorities if there is accepted the UN Security Council (Resolution 2022) dating on 17.05.2015 (consider detail on Part I^[3]). Ultimately, there is unable to link such cases; if any to **Subject 1** ICR, due to reasons sketched in Part I^[3].

Moreover, as Part I^[1] has attempted to highlight there is a lack of reason to equalize children with civilian population, due to Article 50, which obligates to protect children from the effect of the armed conflict. Article 50 of the Geneva law protects explicitly children. As can be seen there are three (3) groups children of very young age, in addition to children between two and six years old as well as six infants with cerebral palsy [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §896]. Owing to the of very young age of the children including individuals infants with cerebral palsy there is presuppose presence of adults in the three groups; thus, implementing, perhaps, civilians, military, and/or border control staff members. It is not specified in the text of [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §896].

Apart, from pro-argument provided *via* Part I^[1], for purpose of this study, I would like to concentrate further on how these and such cases; if any, could be attached wrongly to **Subject 1**; thus, seeking ICR within the AWTs^[2] wording? Since, this part is a continuation of the research on the AWTs^[2] wording, my highlights, herein, are on employment in term “civilians’ and chiefly “policy”.

Since, there still is disagreement and confusion in applying the term ‘civilians’, at this point I would like to turn on its notion of “non-combatants’ under Article 3 to the [Geneva] Conventions, however, I would like to remind that the concept of “non-combatants” is not always clear in application [IT 94-1-T/07.05.1997, § 637]. There could be included resistance fighters or hospital patients. Thus, there, first, becomes unclear what there is understood under “adults” in Paragraph [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025, §896]. Do these people civilians, military, and/or border control staff members as well as do they hospital patients, or, perhaps, more? Apart, from the additional requested elements some of which already mentioned in Part I^[3], herein, I would like to add that within the framework of the concepts of “indiscriminate attack” and “principle of proportionality” [IT-98-29-T/05.12.2003, §§ 57, 58] there is expected the individual who planed the act to verify and classify the adults in the “discussed” case as civilians. Obviously, as occupying a High State Public Elected Official position of President during that time (“two and a half months in the summer of 2014”), there is unable to him and it is outside his authority to exercise any degree of assessment or control over

neither the adults of the group nor Border Control Authority; furthermore, similar to that of military commanders [IT-96-21-T/16.11.1998, §346].

In addition, as can be seen in the cases of the AWT^[2] there is a complete lack of between the act, respectively, attack; if any, and the individual act of the hypothetically accused; thus, referring to point (iv) *a nexus between the individual act and the attack* [ICC-01/09/31.03.2010, §79].

However, owing to his High State Public Elected Official position as President, I would like to sketch on aspects of the *formalization policy*; thus, connecting AWTs^[2] and [EGHR 43800/14/09.07.2025], however, explicitly excluding from any kind of his involvement into these events, due to reasons shown below.

On 30.05.2022 the President of the Russian Federation has signed a Decree 330/30.05.2022, expanding the list of individuals entitled to apply for Russian citizenship under a simplified procedure. [Дополнен перечень лиц, имеющих право обратиться с заявлением о приёме в гражданство России в упрощённом порядке]. There are amendments to Decree 183/24.04.2019 "On Determining, for Humanitarian Purposes, Categories of Persons Entitled to Apply for Admission to Citizenship of the Russian Federation in a Simplified Manner"; and, Decree 187/29.04.2019 "On Certain Categories of Foreign Citizens and Stateless Persons Entitled to Apply for Admission to Citizenship of the Russian Federation in a Simplified Manner."

Decree 330/30.05.2022:

1. *"To establish that orphans and children left without parental care, disabled individuals who are citizens of the Donetsk People's Republic, the Lugansk People's Republic and Ukraine, acquire citizenship of the Russian Federation in a simplified manner in accordance with Part Eight of Article 14 of the Federal Law on May 31, 2002 No. 62-FZ 'On the Citizenship of the Russian Federation'."*

[*"Установить, что дети-сироты и дети, оставшиеся без попечения родителей, недееспособные лица, являющиеся гражданами Донецкой Народной Республики, Луганской Народной Республики и Украины, проиобретаю гражданство Российской Федерации в упрощенном порядке в соответствии с частью восьмой статьи 14 Федерального закона от 31 мая 2002 г. 62-ФЗ "О гражданстве Российской Федерации"*].

Decree 183/24.04.2019:

1. *"To establish that persons permanently residing in the territories of certain districts of the Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine have the right to apply for admission to citizenship of the Russian Federation in a simplified manner in accordance with part eight of Article 14 of the Federal Law of May 31, 2002 No. 62-FZ "On Citizenship of the Russian Federation".*

[*Установить, что лица, постоянно проживающие на территориях отдельных районов Донецкой и Луганской областей Украины, имеют право обратиться с заявлениями о приеме в гражданство Российской Федерации в упрощенном порядке в соответствии с частью восьмой статьи 14 Федерального закона от 31 мая 2002 г. № 62-ФЗ «О гражданстве Российской Федерации»*].

Decree 187/29.04.2019

"In order to protect rights and freedoms of human and citizen, and guided by the generally recognized principles and norms of International Law, as well as in accordance with Article 29 of the Federal Law of May 31, 2002, No. 62-FZ "On the Citizenship of the Russian Federation," I decree:

1. *To grant the right to apply for Russian citizenship under a simplified procedure in accordance with Part Eight of Article 14 of the Federal Law of May 31, 2002, No. 62-FZ "On the Citizenship of the Russian Federation": a) citizens of Ukraine who do not have citizenship (nationality) of another state, who were born and permanently resided in the territories of the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol, and who left the aforementioned territories before March 18, 2014, as well as their children, including adopted children, spouses, and parents; b) stateless persons born and permanently residing in the Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol who left the aforementioned territories before March 18, 2014, as well as their children, including adopted children, spouses, and parents; c) citizens of*

Ukraine and stateless persons holding a migration statute or a temporary residence permit in the Russian Federation (hereinafter referred to as a temporary residence permit)''

, 'В целях защиты прав и свобод человека и гражданина, руководствуясь общепризнанными принципами и нормами международного права, в соответствии со статьей 29 Федерального закона от 31 мая 2002 г. № 62-ФЗ "О гражданстве Российской Федерации" постановляю:

1. Предоставить право обратиться с заявлениями о приеме в гражданство Российской Федерации в упрощенном порядке в соответствии с частью восьмой статьи 14 Федерального закона от 31 мая 2002 г. № 62-ФЗ "О гражданстве Российской Федерации":

а) гражданам Украины, не имеющим гражданства (подданства) другого государства, родившимся и постоянно проживавшим на территориях Республики Крым и г. Севастополя, выехавшим за пределы указанных территорий до 18 марта 2014 г., а также их детям, в том числе усыновленным (удочеренным), супругам и родителям;

б) лицам без гражданства, родившимся и постоянно проживавшим на территориях Республики Крым и г. Севастополя, выехавшим за пределы указанных территорий до 18 марта 2014 г., а также их детям, в том числе усыновленным (удочеренным), супругам и родителям;

в) гражданам Украины и лицам без гражданства, имеющим миграционную карту, разрешение на временное проживание в Российской Федерации (далее - разрешение на временное проживание)''

Owing to the fact that the Citizenship of the Russian Federation is ruled by Federal Law 62-FZ/31.05.2002, further defining individual grounds, conditions and procedure for acquisition, respectively, termination of citizenship of the Russian Federation; thus, also including, herein, the children as a defined group individuals under Article 9 (Citizenship of children), the Presidential Decrees agree with the 62-FZ/31.05.2002. The latter Federal Law itself is amended and supplemented under № 134-FZ/24.04.2020; adopted by the State Duma on 17.04.2020; and approved by the Federation Council on 17.04.2020. The Federal Law No. 134-FZ/24.04.2020 rules amendments to the Federal Law "On the Citizenship of the Russian Federation" in terms of simplifying the procedure for admitting foreign citizens and stateless individuals to Russian Citizenship.

Article 14:

1. Stateless individuals who have reached the age of eighteen and possess legal ability to shall have the right to apply for admission to Citizenship of the Russian Federation under a simplified procedure without complying with the conditions stipulated in Paragraphs "a" and "c" of Part One of Article 13 of this Federal Law, if the underlined individuals had citizenship of the USSR, resided and reside in states that were part of the USSR, and have not acquired citizenship of these states."

Статья 14:

"1. Лица без гражданства, достигшие возраста восемнадцати лет и обладающие дееспособностью, вправе обратиться с заявлениями о приеме в гражданство Российской Федерации в упрощенном порядке без соблюдения условий, предусмотренных пунктами "а" и "в" части первой статьи 13 настоящего Федерального закона, если указанные лица имели гражданство СССР, проживали и проживают в государствах, входивших в состав СССР, и не получили гражданство этих государств."

As can be seen the Decrees treat certain categories of foreign citizens and stateless persons; particularly, highlighting the Donetsk People's Republic, the Lugansk People's Republic and Ukraine in addition to orphans and children left without parental care as well as disabled individuals under Decree 330/30.05.2022.

As has been highlighted in Part I^[3], despite, that the Constitution of the Russian Federation (2020) [(consider the texts of the Constitutions of the Russian federation on 12.12.1993 and 01.07.2020)(Text of the RUSSIAN FEDERATION CONSTITUTION translated by the Constitutional Court for the Opinion (No. 992 / 2020) of the EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR DEMOCRACY THROUGH LAW (VENICE COMMISSION) (Strasbourg, 4 February 2021) [CDL-REF(2021)010] [<https://www.coe.int/en/web/venice-commission/-/opinion-992>]] provides to the Presidency and particularly to **Subject 1**, in this case, a Constitutional Decree power under Article 90(1), the Presidential Decrees should not contradict neither the Constitution, nor the

Federal Laws. The Presidential Decrees have lower legal status comparing with the Constitutional and the Federal Laws of the Russian Federation. Any Presidential decree could be blocked by the Parliament.

The discussion, however aims at underlying aspects of formalization policy involving the Presidency of the Russian Federation into law-making processes having, however, lower legal power. Despite the fact that the Parliament of the Russian Federation delegates a Decree power to the Presidency, they reserve to themselves the right to block his Decree at any time. Thus, the Parliament exercises control over the Executive Authorities within the socio-policy system of Public Power Authority of the Russian Federation. Therefore, he [Subject 1] is unable to bear ICR for and cannot be legally charged as individual of any crimes involving elements 'policy' or 'formalization policy' within the any category crimes under the *Rome Statute*.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Large size *.ppt presentation of Figures 1 and 2 with the relevant references, therein.

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